

NbS Mental Health Impacts Evaluation Methodology

D3.2

JUNE 2025

www.greenincities.eu

Project: 101139730 — GreenInCities — HORIZON-MISS-2023-CLIMA-CITIES-01

Funded by
the European Union

NbS Mental Health Impacts Evaluation Methodology

PROJECT ACRONYM	GRANT AGREEMENT #	PROJECT TITLE
GreenInCities	101139730	GreenInCities

DELIVERABLE REFERENCE NUMBER AND TITLE

D3.2
NbS Mental Health Impacts Evaluation Methodology
Revision: v2.1

AUTHORS

Agnieszka Olszewska-Guizzo	Nicolas Escoffier	Anastasia Kokkinou
NL	NL	NL

CONTRIBUTORS:

Fruzsina Csala	Viktor Bukovski	Indrė Gražulevičiūtė-V ilenišké	Giovanni Pagano	Nicoletta Piersantelli
IAAC	ABUD	KTU	LAND	LAND

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

- ✓ **P Public**
- C Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services

Version History

REVISION	DATE	AUTHOR / Editor	PARTNER	DESCRIPTION
v0.1	6.02.2025	Agnieszka Olszewska-Guizzo	NeuroLandscape (NL)	1st Draft
v0.2	9.06.2025	Nicolas Escoffier, Agnieszka Olszewska-Guizzo, Anastasia Kokkinou	NeuroLandscape (NL)	Version with Contributors and protocol testing input – ready for internal review
v0.3	20.06.2025	Emily Edwards Kaninia, Evelina Faliagka	URBANA	Version with reviewers' comments
v0.3b	21.06.2025	Marco Acri Nika Bronić	UNG	Version with reviewers' comments
v0.4	30.06.2025	Agnieszka Olszewska-Guizzo	NeuroLandscape (NL)	Final version – ready for EC submission
v1.0	30.06.2025	Chiara Farinea Fiona Demeur Andrea Conserva	Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia	Submitted to the European Commission
v.2.0	14.08.2025	Anastasia Kokkinou Agnieszka Olszewska-Guizzo	NeuroLandscape (NL)	Shortened version
v2.1	05.12.2025	Agnieszka Olszewska-Guizzo Fiona Demeur	NeuroLandscape (NL) Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia	Formatting updates and submission to the European Commission

Statement of Originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Project Executive Summary

GreenInCities: Demonstrating Holistic Data-driven Co-Creative Approaches in Nature-Based Solutions towards climate Adaptation and Mitigation

In recent decades, new planning paradigms have reshaped cities. Urban regeneration has renovated public spaces, redeveloped city centres, and established innovation districts. Smart cities have implemented technological systems, such as transport management, water and contamination monitoring, and energy-efficient buildings. A new sustainable approach, including recycling, renaturalization, and recovery, has emerged in response to the demand for environmental sensitivity in urban planning. These strategies have mainly been applied to wealthy areas to attract tourism and companies, repositioning cities in the global economic framework. However, applying these regeneration strategies, smart systems, and renaturalization processes to deprived areas is crucial. These areas tend to face multiple urban problems, such as pollution, social and cultural issues, lack of services and low-quality built environments, and public spaces, leading to issues related to liveability, functionality, quality of life, social cohesiveness, and physical and mental health. Moreover, there is a growing need for climate change adaptation strategies, which has led to the implementation of Nature-based Solutions (NbS). However, a new pattern is emerging, which considers nature as a stakeholder in itself, beyond the ecosystem services it provides. Innovative technologies such as AI, machine learning, and immersive realities are also emerging, which can enhance the accuracy of information delivery and people engagement.

GreenInCities aims to develop methodologies and tools for collaborative climate mitigation and adaptation urban planning approaches, specifically for deprived areas, addressing three main challenges: improving societal readiness level and awareness of vulnerable groups, going beyond classical greening and renaturing interventions, and leveraging cutting edge technologies to enhance co-creation and maximise urban regeneration impacts.

Deliverable Executive Summary

This deliverable, **D3.2 – “NbS Mental Health Impacts Evaluation Methodology”** of the GreenInCities project, introduces the **Neurourbanism Assessment (NUA)**, a comprehensive methodology designed for the in-situ evaluation of urban interventions' impacts on mental health status at the neighborhood scale. This document aims to present the NUA methodology in an accessible manner for diverse stakeholders, including urban planners, policymakers, researchers, and residents.

The NUA methodology is based on the premise that the characteristics of the spaces we live in directly impact mental wellbeing outcomes. Unlike traditional clinical assessments focused on individuals, NUA is centered on the **"diagnosis of the space"**, seeking to understand how the human brain responds to its surroundings so they can be optimized for mental health promotion. It integrates insights from neuroscience and urban planning, leveraging portable **neuroscience technologies** and **citizen science** methods to create more mentally healthy urban spaces.

The core of NUA involves collecting multi-modal data in real-world urban environments, ensuring **ecological validity**. Key inputs include in-situ **neurophysiological measurements**, self-reported wellbeing and lifestyle metrics, community bonding data, and objective environmental quality metrics. Mobile electroencephalogram (EEG) devices are used to capture brain activity (specifically alpha and beta bands) and heart rate as participants move through spaces. Self-reported data is collected via questionnaires including stress, anxiety, and life satisfaction metrics. Participants are recruited from the target area's resident population to ensure **representativeness**. They collect data autonomously using the devices and a smartphone app, over a period of five days. Data is subject to rigorous preprocessing and statistical analysis.

The primary output is the **NUA Index**, an easy-to-understand, numeric score expressed as a percentage, which integrates data from neurophysiology, self-reported wellbeing, community bonding, and living environment quality. This index provides an aggregated measure of a neighbourhood's mental wellbeing status influenced by its environment, allowing for a quick and intuitive grasp of the assessment findings. Further facilitated with a traffic light system, the NUA index allows for easy interpretation of results. The outcomes offer a profile of everyday psychology and brain activity, facilitates *pre/post* comparisons for urban interventions, and shows fluctuations over time.

NUA offers significant contributions by providing **evidence-based, actionable metrics** for various stakeholders. It empowers urban planners and decision-makers to identify areas in need of intervention, prioritize projects based on potential mental health impact, justify investments, and integrate mental health into urban development agendas. Through its foundations in citizen science and participatory approach, it also empowers residents to understand their environment's impact and advocate for changes. Furthermore, NUA can be integrated with digital twins, simulators and mapping tools to enhance urban planning and co-creation processes.

While operating within inherent complexities, the NUA methodology has been tested in real-life scenarios to address potential limitations. Challenges such as ensuring sample representativeness in real-world settings, managing noisy physiological data, accounting for external life events, and navigating the novelty of neuro-technologies were addressed through robust recruitment strategies, technological advancements in portable EEG, rigorous data processing, longitudinal study designs, and the citizen science approach. NUA's sensitivity to environmental conditions like weather is acknowledged, highlighting its strength in capturing the dynamic reality of urban space use and the importance of considering seasonal variations. By turning these perceived limitations into opportunities for deeper understanding and action, NUA serves as a valuable tool for advancing neurourbanism research and informing the creation of urban environments that actively promote mental health and optimal living conditions for all.

The GreenInCities project is implementing NUA in pilot locations in **Slovenia, Greece, and Finland**. More cities adopting NUA methodology allows for better calibration of the NUA index as well as optimization of its interoperability with the digital tools.

Index

1. Introduction	10
1.1 Deliverable Structure	10
1.2 Deliverable Purpose	11
1.3 Target Audience	12
1.4 Reference Documents	12
1.5 Standards & norms	13
1.6 Acronyms	13
1.7 List of Figures	14
1.8 List of Tables	15
1.9 Central Concepts	16
2. Background	21
2.1 Neurourbanism: State of the Art	23
2.2 Research questions, misconceptions and gaps in knowledge addressed by NUA	23
2.3 NUA Opportunities	25
2.3.1 Inclusivity in Public Space Design	25
2.3.2 Technological advancements	27
2.3.3 Methodological advancements	29
2.3.4 NUA - a Citizen's Science Approach	29
3. NUA Methodology	32
3.1 NUA Building blocks	34
3.1.1 Objective neuro-physiological measures	35
3.1.2. Subjective, self-reported measures	37
3.1.3 Spatial and environmental measures	38
3.2 Site Eligibility Criteria	39
3.3 Participant Recruitment	43
3.3.1 Meeting participants where they are: recruitment strategies	44
3.3.2 Tailoring Recruitment for each City	51
3.3.2 Protecting the research participants: safety and ethics	53
3.4 Data collection	54
3.4.1 Protocol overview	54
3.5. Data analysis	56
3.5.1 Preparing Physiological and Self-Report Data for Use	56
4. NUA Outputs	58
4.1 NUA Integrations	59
4.1.1 Connection with digital twins and mapping tools	60
4.1.2 Relevant Initiatives – potential for NUA integrations.	63

4.2 Limitations and risks	63
5. Planning and Management	66
5.1 Resources	66
5.1.1 Personnel	66
5.1.2 Required timing	67
5.1.3 Input data	67
5.1.4 Software and Hardware Selection	68
5.2 Data management	68
5.2.1 Data Storage and Security	68
5.2.2 Data Processing and Analysis	69
5.2.3 Data Sharing, Re-use and Integration	69
5.2.4. Participant rights	70
6. Conclusion	71
References	72
Annexes	81
Annex 1 – NUA Enrolment Questionnaire	81
Annex 2 – NUA digital questionnaires	90
Annex 3 – Study instructions manual	97
Annex 4 – NUA-index- mock-up version	99
Annex 5 - Step-by-Step Procedure for Data Collection	100
Annex 6 – Data Analysis Pipeline and Preprocessing Steps	110
A6.1 Preparing physiological data for use	110
A6.2 Preparing self-report data for use	113
A6.3 Statistical analysis strategies for EEG and Self-report data	114
Annex 7 - Relevant initiatives and potential for NUA integration	117
Annex 8 – Software and Hardware Selection Criteria for NUA	118
A8.1 Software	118
A8.2 Hardware	119
Annex 9 – Standards and Norms Underpinning the NUA Methodology	124
A9.1. Ethical Standards	124
A9.2. Scientific and Research Integrity Standards	124
A9.3. Technical and Safety Standards	125
A9.4. Project-Specific Norms and Policies	125

1. Introduction

1.1 Deliverable Structure

This deliverable is structured to provide a comprehensive and accessible guide through the NUA methodology. The document follows a logical progression and is designed to inform a diverse readership.

1. Introduction

Chapter 1 articulates the NUA Methodology and identifies its broad target audience. This chapter also establishes foundational references, ethical standards, and a list of essential abbreviations and central concepts.

2. Background

Chapter 2, defines the emerging field of Neurourbanism, discussing its current state, addressing key research gaps, and highlighting the opportunities NUA presents through technological and methodological advancements.

3. NUA Methodology

Chapter 3 details the practical implementation of NUA. This section covers the method's building blocks, outlines site eligibility criteria, participant recruitment strategies, data collection protocols, and rigorous data analysis procedures for both physiological and self-report data. (All identifiable participants presented in photos of this section have given permission to publish their photo by signing a Media Consent form).

4. NUA Outputs

Chapter 4 shifts focus to the meaningful insights derived from NUA. It introduces the central NUA-Index, an intuitive numeric score for assessing the impact of urban interventions on mental health. This chapter also discusses NUA's integration with digital twins (MHDT) and urban mapping tools for co-creation processes, while transparently acknowledging its inherent limitations and proposed mitigation strategies.

5. Planning and Management

Chapter 5 provides essential guidance for NUA implementation. It covers required resources, including personnel, timing, necessary software and hardware (such as criteria for EEG device selection), comprehensive data management procedures emphasizing security and participant rights, and a detailed risk assessment framework.

6. Conclusion - Chapter 6 summarises NUA's contribution to fostering healthier urban environments. Supplementary materials, such as questionnaires and

examples of NUA results, are provided in the Appendices, followed by a list of literature References.

1.2 Deliverable Purpose

This deliverable, D3.2, serves to comprehensively define, articulate the NeuroUrbanism Assessment (NUA) methodology and position it within the scientific frame. The core purpose is to provide an accessible, step-by-step guide for in-situ evaluation of urban interventions' impacts on mental health status at the neighbourhood scale. NUA offers evidence-based, actionable metrics that support the creation of mentally healthy living environments. Figure 1 illustrates a general overview of NUA's key inputs and outputs. For instance, NUA can quantify improvements in neighbourhood community's wellbeing metrics, such as a 20% increase in community bonding, following spatial interventions like park transformations, thereby demonstrating tangible benefits.

Figure 1. General inputs and outputs of NUA.

Ultimately, this document aims to facilitate evidence-based urban planning and design, comparative analysis across neighbourhoods, and continuous mental health monitoring over time, enabling stakeholders to identify high-impact projects and justify urban decisions.

1.3 Target Audience

The NUA method is designed to benefit a diverse array of stakeholders committed to fostering greener and healthier urban neighbourhoods, primarily focusing on decision-makers in urban planning and design. Although calibrated and first tested in the European context, the NUA approach holds **global applicability**, offering benefits to urban decision-makers worldwide.

The core stakeholders include:

- **Public bodies** at European, national, regional, and local levels, such as the European Commission, National Ministries, Municipal Planning Departments, and Metropolitan Planning Agencies (e.g., Greater London Authority, Berlin Senate Department for Urban Development).
- **Specialized urban planning agencies** (e.g., Danish Architecture Center, Finnish Environment Institute).
- **Research institutes and think tanks** (e.g., Institute for European Environmental Policy, Centre for Cities).
- **International and intergovernmental organizations** (e.g., United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, OECD).

Beyond these foundational decision-making bodies, NUA also serves:

- **Design professionals** (architects, landscape architects, urban planners). NUA provides them with in-depth, nuanced, and site-specific user profiles for on-site research, and acts as a powerful tool demonstrating the impact of their designs and monitoring current post-occupancy performance.
- **Multidisciplinary researchers and academics** globally. They can utilize NUA to capture ecologically valid, in-situ data, combining environmental, physiological, and psychological measures to advance the understanding of human-environment relationships within urban contexts.
- **Citizens (society at large)**. NUA empowers the citizens in the decision-making process by making them a part of city dynamics.

1.4 Reference Documents

This deliverable was developed following the GreenInCities Grant Agreement (#101139730) and the Consortium Agreement and is outlined by the project's Deliverable **D1.1 - Project Management Plan**.

The integration of NUA within the GreenInCities project aligns with multiple deliverables that focus on urban mapping, citizen science, and digital twinning. More specifically with: **D4.1 - Ethics and Data Requirements**, ensuring responsible collection of

neuro-data; **D7.3 - Interventions' Impact Assessment**; and **D7.4 - Inclusivity Plan, promoting citizen engagement in mental health-aware urban design**.

Additionally, it directly connects with the Urban Simulation and Digital Twin Tools developed under WP4 and WP5, more specifically: **D5.1 - Leader Cities Site Analysis** and **D5.2 - Co-created plans and interventions report**, which serve as the core digital framework for integrating neuroscience-driven urban planning strategies.

1.5 Standards & norms

The Neurourbanism Assessment (NUA) methodology is grounded in rigorous scientific and ethical standards to ensure valid, reliable, and safe research outcomes. Central to its design is the protection of participants through informed consent, confidentiality, the right to withdraw without penalty, and clear communication about data use. Classified as minimal risk, the study uses non-invasive, CE-marked portable neuroscience devices requiring no specialized training. NUA ensures scientific integrity through real-world (in-situ) data collection, validated preprocessing of physiological signals, standardized self-report handling, and robust statistical methods. The approach is participatory, incorporating citizen science principles to enhance ecological validity and community engagement. All data management complies with GDPR and follows the GreenInCities Data Management Plan (D1.8), ensuring ethical handling, secure storage, and responsible use of sensitive data. For details on standards and norms underpinning the NUA Methodology see **Annex 9**.

1.6 Acronyms

The table below outlines the abbreviations and acronyms to be utilised throughout the project.

Table 1: Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
BFSG	Barrierefreiheitsstärkungsgesetz
CE	Conformité Européenne - Compliance for Electrical Equipment
CEB	Council of Europe Development Bank
CLM	Contemplative Landscape Model
EAA	European Accessibility Act

EC	European Commission
EO	Ethics Overseer
EEG	Electroencephalography
EKG	Electrocardiogram
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GA	Grant Agreement
mEEG	Mobile electroencephalography
MHDT	Mental Health Digital Twin
NDA	Non-disclosure Agreement
NUA	Neurourbanism Assessment
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
WHO	World Health Organization
URBACT	European exchange and learning programme promoting sustainable urban development

1.7 List of Figures

Table 2: List of Figures

Figure #	Title	Page #
Figure 1	General inputs and outputs of NUA	11
Figure 2	Urbanisation in 2018 and 2030 projections	21
Figure 3	Share of population with mental illness in the GreenInCities pilot countries (IHME, Global Burden of Disease (2024).	22
Figure 4	Evolution of EEG technology: A. an early Electro-Encephalograph, study by Mr W G Carradine (in chair), London 1947 and B. mEEG device during recording outdoors, Cyprus, 2024.	28
Figure 5	Determinants of urban health, adapted from (Whitehead & Dahlgren, 1991).	34

Figure 6	Different types of measures integrated into NUA-index.	35
Figure 7	Neighborhood unit components (Image credit: Perry, 2004)	41
Figure 8	On-site recruitment of the local residents, at the public library, Nova Gorica, April 2025.	45
Figure 9	Instagram posts about the NUA in Nova Gorica, inviting residents to participate.	47
Figure 10	The resident's journey from the NUA data collection.	49
Figure 11	NUA participants signing consent forms, during the enrolment meeting, April 2025, Nova Gorica, Slovenia.	55
Figure 12	NUA protocol overview. Steps for post-intervention (T2) assessment are identical, except for administrative steps marked (T1) which are only conducted at the first assessment before intervention.	56
Figure 13	A. Examples of different NUA-indices represented with percentage values as well as the traffic-light system. B. NUA scale with colour coding referent to the traffic light system.	58
Figure 14	Potential integration of NUA within the stages of the co-creation process.	61
Figure 15	Team of Researchers from NeuroLandscape	71

1.8 List of Tables

Table 3: List of Tables

Table #	Title	Page #
Table 1	Abbreviations and Acronyms	13
Table 2	List of Figures	14
Table 3	List of Tables	15
Table 4	Central Concepts and definitions around NUA.	16
Table 5	Self-reported questionnaires integrated in NUA	36

Table 6	Environmental measurements in NUA	38
Table 8	Summary guide to select spatial unit for NUA assessment	43
Table 9	Recruitment strategies and their yield in participants.	52
Table 10	Risks and risk mitigation measures of NUA.	64

1.9 Central Concepts

This section outlines the key concepts underlying NUA. The method itself involves multidisciplinary insights from science and design, more specifically neuroscience and urban planning and design. Researchers and professionals in these disciplines use different concepts in their research and even some common concepts are interpreted and applied in different contexts. In Table 4, we listed out the set of standard terminologies for clarity and easy reader reference. This set of terms and concepts was based on our current body of knowledge for 2025; however, this field evolves rapidly, and some definitions might need refinement over time. Additionally, this list is not meant to be exhaustive, rather encompassing the most used terms and concepts. It will help readers from any discipline to get a basic understanding of concepts that will be used and referred to throughout the project and in other documents.

Table 4. Central Concepts and definitions around NUA.

Term	Definition	Ref.
Artifacts	Any undesirable noise or signals from electrophysiological recording that do not reflect and mask biological or neurological data of interest.	(Cohen, 2014)
Baseline data	Measurement conducted before the actual recording or assessment which captures individual differences and allows to compute relative changes.	(Cohen, 2014)
Brain activity	Neural processes that can be measured using electrophysiological measures or other imaging techniques.	(Nunez & Srinivasan, 2006)
Built environment	The man-made or modified structures that provide people with living, working, and recreational spaces.	EPA ¹

¹ <https://www.epa.gov/smm/basic-information-about-built-environment>

Control	In experiment design, a comparison condition without treatment or intervention which allows isolating the effect of the intervention.	Shadish et al., 2002
Ecological validity	The ability of research findings drawn from an experiment or an assessment to generalise to real world environments and behaviour.	(Bronfenbrenner, 1977)
EEG channels	Standardised location of recording electrodes on the scalp for neurophysiological recording, which ensures consistent and comparable spatial coverage of the underlying brain activity.	(Jasper, 1958)
EKG (Electrocardiogram)	Recording of the heart electrical activity performed using electrodes placed on the skin, which reflects its functioning.	(Wagner & Strauss, 2014)
Environmental psychology	Discipline that studies the interplay between people, places and the environment. This includes the impact of the built and natural environment on people's experiences, wellbeing and actions.	(Abrahamse, 2019)
Epochs	Separate time segments cut-out from a continuous neurophysiological recording.	(Cohen, 2014)
Experiment	A research process that manipulates one or several conditions or variables to determine its impact on a measured outcome.	(Brewer & Crano, 2000)
Exposure	Interactions between participant and specific environment or set of conditions as part of a research study or a set of conditions.	(Rothman, 2008)
Fourier Transform (FFT)	An algorithmic operation which decomposes signals recorded over time into their individual frequency component which allow frequency level analysis of physiological recordings.	(Cooley & Tukey, 1965)
Health	Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social wellbeing and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity.	WHO ²
Health promotion	The process of enabling people to increase control over, and to improve, their health. It moves beyond a focus on individual behaviour towards a wide range of social and	WHO ³

² [Mental health \(who.int\)](https://www.who.int) accessed on 18.07.2024

³ <https://www.who.int/westernpacific/about/how-we-work/programmes/health-promotion#:~:text=As%20a%20core%20of%20community%20action%20and%20personal%20skills>. Accessed on 18.07.2024

	<p>environmental interventions.</p> <p>Unlike the healthcare infrastructure, health promotion supports governments, communities and individuals to cope with and address health challenges. This is accomplished by building healthy public policies, creating supportive environments, and strengthening community action and personal skills.</p>	
Heart rate (HR)	Measure of the number of heartbeats per minute.	(Berntson et al., 1997)
Heart rate variability (HRV)	Changes in time interval between subsequent heartbeats, which reflects autonomous nervous system activation.	(Berntson et al., 1997)
Human-centric design	An approach advocating that urbanism should focus on a person's relationship to the environment	(Gehl, 2013; Roe & McCay, 2021; Tuan, 1997)
Informed Consent	Process of providing full information to participants about a research study risks and benefits so they can make an informed decision about their participation.	(Beauchamp & Childress, 1994)
Intervention	A change implemented by land management at the neighbourhood scale, in order to improve the living conditions of people and the environment.	IGI global dictionary ⁴
In-situ	Research conducted in a real life environment as opposed to controlled artificial lab environments.	(Brewer & Crano, 2000)
Landscape	A lived, embodied, and interpreted space that emerges through human perception, cultural memory, and existential engagement with the environment. It is a dynamic, relational field where meaning is co-constituted by the observer and the world.	(Heidegger, 1951; Ingold, 1993; Tuan, 2011)
Living Environment	Immediate physical, social, and psychological surroundings in which individuals or communities reside, work, and interact. It encompasses both built (e.g., homes, infrastructure, urban design) and natural (e.g., green spaces, air quality, water) elements that directly influence human health, well-being, and behaviour.	WHO ⁵

⁴<https://www.igi-global.com/dictionary/concept-and-approach-to-land-management-interventions-for-rural-development-in-africa/66345#:~:text=Any%20change%20caused%20by%20land.of%20people%20and%20the%20environment.>

Accessed on 18.07.2024

⁵ https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/108180/EUR_ICP_LVNG_01_07_02.pdf

Mental Health	Mental health is a state of wellbeing in which an individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and is able to contribute to his or her community.	WHO ²
Neighbourhood	Comprehensive residential systems in rural, peri-urban or urban areas with mixed functions. A neighbourhood ideally includes public and private functions and infrastructures such as education institutions (e.g. kindergartens, primary schools), cultural facilities, community centres, youth centres, retirement homes, post offices, banks, stores, parks, and workplaces. Neighbourhoods are where people live, socialise and find services to meet a substantial part of their daily needs. In contrast to communities, which are social units, neighbourhood refers to a physical unit where one can address local-level challenges through planning initiatives.	Horizon Europe Work Program (2025) 13. NEB Facility ⁶
Neuroscience	Study of the nervous system – from structure to function, development to degeneration, in health and in disease. It covers the whole nervous system, with a primary focus on the brain.	Kings College of London ⁷
Neurourbanism	Interdisciplinary approach that connects public mental health to urban planning to create better environments that will improve the mental wellbeing of individuals and communities in cities and strengthen the resilience of high-risk individuals and children.	(Adli et al., 2017)
Participant	Individuals who voluntarily take part in a research study.	(Brewer & Crano, 2000)
Phenomenological approach	The understanding or mapping (of a place or context) is better achieved through immersing within the real scenario	(Snodgrass & Coyne, 2013)
Population	Full group of individuals from which are drawn participants of a research study or assessment, and to which final findings are expected to generalise.	(Brewer & Crano, 2000)
Preprocessing pipeline	A step-by-step sequence of operations performed on raw neurophysiological recordings to prepare them for quantitative analysis.	(Luck, 2014)

⁶https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2025/wp-13-new-european-bauhaus-facility_horizon-2025_en.pdf

⁷<https://www.kcl.ac.uk/neuroscience/about/what-is-neuroscience> accessed on 18.07.2024

Public mental health	Actions oriented at improving mental health and wellbeing and preventing mental illness through the organised efforts and informed choices of society, organisations, public and private, communities and individuals.	FPH ⁸
Raw data	Original unprocessed data as delivered by recording devices or collection processes.	(Luck, 2014)
Sampling rate	The frequency at which an analogue, continuous, signal is transformed into a series of discrete digital signal measurements.	(Nyquist, 2009)
Stress	Natural human response to challenges, but chronic stress can become a risk factor for mental health conditions such as depression and anxiety, as well as physical illnesses like cardiovascular disease.	(Chu et al., 2024)
Tracking	The monitoring of participants behaviour or electrophysiological processes over time.	(Shiffman et al., 2008)
WEIRD sample	Western, Educated, Industrialized, Rich, and Democratic, type of samples often used in neuroscience research studies, particularly those conducted in controlled laboratory environments, where participants are typically university students	(Pitesa & Gelfand, 2023)
Wellbeing	A construct encompassing how people feel and function both personally and socially, including their subjective evaluation of life satisfaction, positive emotions, and a sense of meaning.	(Jarden & Roache, 2023)

8

<https://www.fph.org.uk/policy-advocacy/special-interest-groups/public-mental-health-special-interest-group/better-mental-health-for-all/why-public-mental-health-matters/#:~:text=Public%20mental%20health%20is%20the.and%20private%2C%20communities%20and%20individuals.>
Accessed on 18.07.2024

2. Background

Figure 2: Urbanisation in 2018 and 2030 projections, source: (Olszewska-Guizzo, Fogel, Benjumea, et al., 2022).

Urbanisation is “one of the twenty-first century’s most transformative trends” as per the United National Assembly (2016). It is further estimated that by 2050, even 68% of the global population will reside in metropolitan areas (Yemeru; et al., 2024). As the global urban population grows exponentially, urban inhabitants face a vast array of socioeconomic inequalities or environmental problems and are at higher risk of developing mental health disorders. Globally, the main challenges to mental health in urban areas include loneliness, violence, high crime rates, homelessness, noise and other pollutants, traffic accidents, drug abuse, and insufficiency of mental health services (Okkels et al., 2018). At the same time, the most prevalent

mental health illness groups are mood and anxiety disorders. The same is visible in the European Region (WHO, 2021). Given the available evidence it is possible to attribute the upward trend of the mental health (MH) diseases in rapidly urbanized areas to the specificity of living in the metropolitan areas.

It is an already established consensus that the perception and interaction with the living environment shape the development of the human brain—from early stages to maturity, further impacting the state of mental health and wellbeing (Dolan, 2002). For instance, it has been demonstrated by meta-analyses that the urban population is more likely to develop anxiety or depressive symptoms than rural residents (Peen et al., 2010; van der Wal et al., 2021). Available evidence points towards two major predictors of an increased prevalence of MH disorders of the “urban brain”: social stress, including both social density and social isolation (Lederbogen et al., 2011), and environmental factors, expressed mainly through the lack or unequal access to health-protective resources, such as natural environments (Olszewska-Guizzo, Fogel, Benjumea, et al., 2022). The human brain, through a complex network of neural connections, is at the heart of our homeostatic control and the way we act to environmental exposures. The brain determines what is threatening, as well as the behavioural and physiological adaptive

responses (Grande et al., 2020; Jacobs & Appleyard, 1987). Some of these reactivity patterns are advantageous in the short-term, but if experienced for prolonged time they can become maladaptive. Such detrimental effects impact our brain capacity to regulate peripheral physiology, engage in adaptive social and health behaviours, and experience and control emotions (McEwen & Gianaros, 2010).

The biological underpinnings of these observations have not yet been fully explored; however some studies indicated the causal influences of particular environmental exposures (e.g., comparison between urban vs natural images by Tost and colleagues (Tost et al., 2015) or contemplative vs non-contemplative landscape scenes by some of the authors of this deliverable (Olszewska-Guizzo, Fogel, Escoffier, et al., 2022)).

The increasing mental health challenges associated with urban living necessitate innovative approaches to understanding and addressing the interplay between urban environments and psychological wellbeing. Fields such as environmental psychology, environmental neuroscience, offer new perspectives by bridging the gaps between environmental exposure, brain function, and mental health outcomes. Recognizing this critical need, GreenInCities strives to pioneer solutions rooted in these disciplines. These solutions are to be applied in five pilot sites across Europe and further replicated in six follower sites, within different socio-environmental contexts and urban morphologies (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Share of population with mental illness in the GreenInCities pilot countries (IHME, Global Burden of Disease (2024)). * GreenInCities frontrunner countries, ^ countries selected for NUA testing.

By integrating research and applied methodologies, we aim to foster urban environments that promote mental health and wellbeing. These goals are aligned with and find a natural framework in an emerging discipline, that of neurourbanism.

2.1 Neurourbanism: State of the Art

Neurourbanism is an emerging discipline which is currently gaining momentum as an independent research field in the multidisciplinary research world. It bridges insights from environmental neuroscience and neuroarchitecture to understand the complex intersections between the built environment and human health and wellbeing. While neuroarchitecture primarily applies to buildings and infrastructure, neurourbanism adopts a wider perspective, encompassing the entire cityscape, including natural elements and networks.

Urban health research has predominantly focused on the impacts of urban environments on physical health, rather than mental health and wellbeing (e.g. Rigolon et al., 2021). Moreover, most studies have relied on cross-sectional, correlational designs, which reveal associations but not causality, leaving neurobiological mechanisms of nature's mental health benefits poorly understood. On the other hand, traditional neuroscience experiments have been limited by lab-based neuroscience methods that lack ecological validity. This means their findings may not generalize to real-world environments and behaviours. Given the dynamic nature of urban environments, the only way to achieve this is through living labs approaches and in-situ measurements, leveraging portable and mobile brain imaging devices like mobile electroencephalography (mEEG) tools.

The principle of ecological validity also extends to study participants. Ideally, participants should be recruited from the local resident population to account for socio-economic and socio-demographic differences in perceptions and use of public spaces. Observational studies often include residents, but experimental studies frequently use convenience sampling, typically university students (Berman et al., 2008), leading to "WEIRD" (Western, Educated, Industrialized, Rich, and Democratic) samples. Such samples limit the generalizability of neuroscience research results to the diverse urban context (Pitesa & Gelfand, 2023).

The GreenInCities project, with its Neurourbanism Assessment (NUA), offers a unique opportunity to address these limitations by combining mobile neuroimaging methods with participatory and place-based strategies. It seeks to understand how urban environments affect psychological states and to integrate these insights into inclusive urban design and policy.

2.2 Research questions, misconceptions and gaps in knowledge addressed by NUA

The Neurourbanism Assessment (NUA) methodology is specifically designed to address several critical issues and prevailing knowledge gaps in the field of urban mental health. NUA is an approach to transforming cities into intentionally mentally healthy living environments by bridging interdisciplinary scientific rigor with actionable urban planning. It reveals the hidden emotional and cognitive signatures of spaces, showing how urban design can profoundly influence our minds.

1. **Prevailing deficiency in interdisciplinary research** that aims at comprehending the influence of urban factors on mental health and wellbeing (Manning, 2019). This is followed by the pressing need to translate this knowledge into practice of urban planning and design (Olszewska-Guizzo et al., 2022). While neurourbanism is predominantly defined by its interdisciplinary nature, joining neuroscience and urban studies, it embraces **transdisciplinarity**, incorporating environmental psychology, public health, computer science, and citizen science into its collaborative framework. This deeper integration is crucial to tackle real-world urban challenges and requires active participation from diverse stakeholders, including municipalities, policymakers, urban practitioners, and citizens alike.
 - **Citizen science approach.** Even though participatory approaches in urban planning are gaining momentum, they still provide only limited contribution from citizens in the final urban design outcomes (Ramadier, 2004). NUA is one more attempt to ameliorate this by engaging the citizens in the neurourbanism data collection already before any intervention is implemented. This potentially leads to bottom-up co-creations of more mentally-healthy living environments, with features and Nature-based Solutions inspired and crafted for the specific needs the residents of a given area need the most.
 - **Ecological validity.** NUA addresses challenges of ecological validity discussed previously though fostering two or more time-point study designs and collecting data in situ from direct users of the urban environment. This allows the study of causal relationships between space and mental health, explaining the mechanisms of health promotion and the long-term benefits of urbanist interventions in a more generalisable manner.
2. **Nature-Based Solutions (NbS) quality over quantity.** It is now widely recognized that not all natural environments have the same potential for promoting health (Beute et al., 2023; Jarvis et al., 2020). Research, including that by Agnieszka Olszewska-Guizzo, (Olszewska-Guizzo, 2023) indicates that only specific aspects and scenic elements aggregated within the natural landscapes can induce desired brain responses. In the context of experiencing the outdoor

urban environments, these particular landscape scenes were described and classified through the quantitative assessment tool called “Contemplative Landscape Model”. It was created to systematically identify the most beneficial environmental exposures (Olszewska-Guizzo, 2023; Olszewska-Guizzo, Escoffier, et al., 2022). NUA seeks to consolidate knowledge in this area, demonstrating that optimally designed green spaces, incorporating properly implemented nature-based solutions, will yield greater positive impacts on human wellbeing and socio-ecological benefits.

NUA aims to inform urban planning and design, by providing scientific evidence on the effects of different urban scenarios on brain activity. Instead of implementing spatial interventions based often on architectural trends or designers’ intuition, neurourbanism approaches enable evidence-backed, wellbeing-oriented interventions. NUA’s goal is also to inform health promotion, while complementing, rather than replacing, clinical medicine or pharmacological treatments. It still can inform the design of therapeutic landscapes for patients with neurodegenerative diseases. Importantly though, it can address collective communities’ challenges, such as supporting refugees coping with trauma by creating calming, inclusive residential spaces. The health-promoting value of interaction with spaces is backed by a growing body of research highlighting the mental health benefits of green and blue spaces.

The GreenInCities project aims to address all these identified knowledge gaps and research questions, developing a systematic approach bolstered by public authorities, citizens, and academia, thereby laying the groundwork for a new urban wellbeing methodology.

2.3 NUA Opportunities

Building on the background and core concepts previously discussed, NUA offers distinct potentials in several key areas for advancing our understanding and application of neurourbanism principles. We begin by examining the potential of NUA to support **Inclusivity in Public Space Design**, focusing on how the methodology can contribute to creating urban environments that better enhance the mental health and wellbeing of all users. Following this, the chapter will explore how NUA leverages recent **Technological and methodological advancements**, highlighting the use of portable neurophysiological tools for conducting real-world assessments of the urban environment’s impact on mental health. We conclude this chapter with discussing the tendency of **Citizen’s science approach** in research and how NUA can address it.

2.3.1 *Inclusivity in Public Space Design*

The common ground for inclusivity and accessibility is to remove barriers that exclude any social group. Conventionally, one of the main determinants of inclusive or universal public space design is the accessibility to these spaces and/or services they provide (Murray et al., 2004). Although accessibility is not the only criterion of an inclusive space – this term is much broader and integrates many aspects and characteristics of the spaces, and the ways they were created. We argue here that inclusivity of public spaces also means how they consider all users’ mental health and wellbeing during the design phase as well as the post-occupancy stage.

Current standards and regulations are rooted in universal design principles such as equitable use, intuitive layout, and low physical effort (Lidwell et al., 2010). These are reflected in legal frameworks like the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (Assembly, 2006) and the European Accessibility Act (EU 2019/882), which guides how environments and products must meet accessibility goals, including through standards like EN 17210 and related technical reports. While these frameworks focus on removing physical barriers, they often stop short of addressing mental health, sensory needs, or social inclusion. Certification systems such as Germany’s BFG and BREEAM In-Use expand this scope by incorporating social and emotional considerations, such as rest areas, care facilities, and support for diverse gender needs (BRE, 2020). Below two case examples of good practices are presented showcasing the need for spaces for all and the multidimensionality of inclusivity.

Good practice #1	ST PAUL’S CATHEDRAL
	<i>Year: 2021</i>
	<i>Location: London, United Kingdom</i>
	<i>Size: 50 m²</i>

This project is an accessibility improvement to a historic religious and tourist site. St Paul’s (built 1675–1708) is a Grade I listed cathedral. The Equal Access project created a dignified new entrance so that people who use wheelchairs and others with limited mobility can enter the cathedral’s main level alongside everyone else, rather than using side or back entrances.

Inclusivity goes beyond accessibility by addressing not only physical barriers but also social and cultural ones. While certifications like BFG focus on physical access, BREEAM expands the scope to include amenities for all genders, rest and care facilities, and spaces for social interaction (BRE, 2020). The UK Design Council emphasizes that inclusive design extends “well beyond physical access,” incorporating gender inclusiveness, affordability, and public participation (Horwill & Thomas, 2019). These dimensions recognize that barriers can be socially constructed, not just ability based. The New European Bauhaus (NEB) formalizes this broader view, promoting diversity, affordability, and participation as core principles (EC, 2021).

Good
practice
#2

DE HOGWEYK

Year: 2009

Location: Amsterdam, the Netherlands

Size: 11000 m²

De Hogeweyk is a specialized residential complex for elderly people with severe dementia, designed to mimic a normal small town. It functions as a long-term care facility but in the form of an open, walkable village. Houses are designed like regular homes (each with its own front door, kitchen, living room) and each caters to a certain lifestyle group. All buildings are single or two-story and fully accessible, with subtle cues to assist people with cognitive impairment, and the social spaces are open to visiting families and even the public.

A growing body of academic research in environmental psychology and public health indicates that the design aspects— accessibility, sensory qualities, social inclusiveness, etc. can influence stress levels, mood, and overall mental health outcomes for users through a variety of mechanisms:

- Better accessibility is associated with reduced stress and general wellbeing
- Better environmental legibility is associated with reduced anxiety
- Reduction of loneliness through environments encouraging interactions
- Sensory design is associated with specific emotional effects

By foregrounding these dimensions, NUA leverages inclusive design not only to assess environments but to enable real-world, participatory, and ecologically valid data collection. Rather than merely evaluating physical access, NUA helps identify and promote environments that foster social connection, and mental wellbeing, especially for populations often excluded from standard research and design practices.

2.3.2 Technological advancements

The NUA methodology rests on recent technological advancements in the world of electroencephalographic recording. These technologies aim at recording human brainwaves, which reflect the underlying brain activity. Especially relevant to the NUA methodology are recent advancements related to wireless and portable tools to record human EEG data. In what follows, we will present these, highlighting how they constitute a unique and timely opportunity leveraged by NUA.

- **Miniaturisation of EEG amplifiers:** EEG amplifiers have become compact, lightweight, and portable, allowing data collection outside of laboratory environments.
- **Wireless data transmission (Bluetooth, Wi-Fi):** Wireless protocols enable real-time data streaming without cables, allowing participants to move freely during recordings.
- **High-capacity compact batteries:** Modern batteries support longer recording sessions while remaining lightweight and easy to carry.

- **Improved data storage components:** Small and reliable storage units can hold large volumes of data, enabling continuous, unsupervised recordings.
- **Active electrodes:** These electrodes include built-in preamplifiers, improving signal quality by reducing noise in mobile conditions.
- **Dry electrodes:** These do not require conductive gels, making setup faster and easier, and enabling participants to apply them independently.
- **Consumer-grade EEG devices:** Devices originally developed for wellness markets are now usable for research, due to their ease of use and accessibility.
- **Smartphone use and digital literacy:** The widespread use of smartphones allows participants to install apps, manage recordings, and transfer data with minimal assistance.

These advancements collectively enable **portable, scalable, and participant-driven EEG research**, central to NUA's mission of conducting ecologically valid, inclusive, and participatory studies in real-world urban settings (Figure 4A,B).

Figure 4. Evolution of EEG technology: A. an early Electro-Encephalograph, study by Mr W G Carradine (in chair), London 1947 and B. mEEG device during recording outdoors, Cyprus, 2024.

2.3.3 Methodological advancements

NUA uses several methodological advancements to ensure the usefulness, robustness and accuracy of its assessment of the impact of environmental changes on residents.

Ecological validity

Ecological validity has long referred to studying human responses in real-world settings rather than artificial lab environments (Brunswik, 1955). The advances in mEEG covered in the previous section have facilitated this approach. The NUA in situ recording, with a focus on investigating the mental health and wellbeing of residents, allows a more naturalistic capture of their response to their everyday environment, whether there are stressors or resourcing experiences, and their impact on how residents cope with those real-life stressors. Together, this allows much more powerful and useful conclusions to be drawn and grounds design decisions in locally valid in situ data.

mEEG methodological developments for in situ assessment

The key methodological developments that support NUA in situ assessment are advances in processing and analysis of mEEG recorded in the field. These are focused on mitigating the impact of real-life recording on the accuracy of the data. Unlike laboratory recordings where participants are still, the most ecologically valid assessments will involve moving participants. Movement is a source of artefacts in mEEG recording that can decrease the accuracy of the conclusions derived from the assessment. A set of mature technologies have been developed and are leveraged in NUA that allow the suppression or control of the consequences of movement on in situ recording.

Two key techniques are used to mitigate motion-related artefacts:

- **Artefact Subspace Reconstruction (ASR):** Automatically detects and repairs noisy data by referencing clean segments from the same recording (Mullen et al., 2015; Callan et al., 2024).
- **Independent Component Analysis (ICA):** Decomposes EEG signals to isolate and remove artefacts like eye blinks or body movement, increasingly enhanced by machine learning (Hsu et al., 2018; Radüntz et al., 2017).

Taken together, these two approaches allow the removal of pragmatic interference from movement in free-moving participants in real environments, which allows benefiting from the advantages of ecological validity of in situ recording whilst preserving the data quality that allows accurate and precise assessment.

2.3.4 NUA - a Citizen's Science Approach

Citizen science refers to the active participation of non-scientists in scientific research. The term was independently popularized in the mid-1990s by Alan Irwin and Rick Bonney. Irwin (2002) defined "*citizen science*" as a form of scientific citizenship that

opens science and policy processes to the public, emphasizing the responsibility of science to society and the capacity of citizens to contribute knowledge.

Citizen science enables research at scales otherwise impractical (Bonney et al., 2014), spanning diverse fields from astronomy to public health. This approach yields massive datasets and novel scientific insights, and brings societal benefits such as public education, empowerment, and stronger trust in science (Bonney et al., 2016). Importantly, citizen science helps bridge the gap between science and society.

Over the past decade, formal frameworks and support structures for citizen science have emerged. An international community of practitioners developed the “Ten Principles of Citizen Science” as guidelines for high-quality projects, emphasizing inclusivity, data quality, feedback, and societal impact (Robinson et al., 2018). Major institutions have also embraced citizen science. In the United States, the Crowdsourcing and Citizen Science Act of 2016 authorized federal agencies to engage the public in research, and the European Commission has integrated citizen science into its Open Science policy and funding programs (Commission et al., 2020). Dedicated associations (e.g., the Citizen Science Association and the European Citizen Science Association) provide networks, develop best practices, and advocate for the field (Robinson et al., 2018). This growing ecosystem of principles, policies, and organizations has legitimized citizen science as an integral part of the scientific enterprise.

Urban planners leverage citizen-generated data and local knowledge to inform decisions on issues such as land use, transportation, and environmental health (Beck & Mitkiewicz, 2025). Common methods include participatory mapping (citizens identifying local features and issues on shared maps), crowdsourced reporting of problems (via mobile or web apps), and community environmental monitoring using low-cost sensors (e.g., for air quality or noise). Such tools expand the spatial and temporal granularity of urban data beyond what official surveys can achieve, providing real-time, hyper-local and highly ecologically valid insights. For instance, residents have collected localized air pollution and traffic data, revealing hotspots that prompted municipal action. In urban design, innovative projects have used video games (e.g., Minecraft for co-designing public spaces,) and crowd-mapping of perceived safety in public spaces to incorporate diverse voices (Melanie Davern et al., 2022).

Recent innovations and research in this domain focus on integrating citizen science more deeply into professional planning and on addressing remaining challenges. Reported benefits include greater community engagement, improved environmental monitoring, and more data-driven, sustainable planning (Beck & Mitkiewicz, 2025).

Another emerging direction is applying citizen science to urban social and individual wellbeing issues such as examining how neighborhood environments affect residents’ wellbeing and mental health (Klement et al., 2025). NUA aligns very well with this

approach by inviting the local residents, direct recipients and users of built environment and local urban interventions to collect their own mental health data, including the brain imaging data, using simple, easy to operate mobile EEG devices.

3. NUA Methodology

Neurourbanism Assessment (NUA) is a method to evaluate the impact of the built environment on people's mental wellbeing and is based on the premise that the types and characteristics of the spaces we live in directly impact the short and long-term wellbeing outcomes. As a result, it provides an easy to understand, numeric NUA index. NUA index integrates in-situ neurophysiological measurement (mEEG, HR), self-reported wellbeing and lifestyle metrics, community bonding and environmental quality metrics. NUA brings several key contributions and benefits to cities and their stakeholders:

- It can be utilized to **demonstrate the extent of success of specific urban interventions** by evaluating their direct impact on mental health and wellbeing metrics, such as stress levels, mood, and quality of life. This is achieved by comparing mental health profiles before and after an intervention, like the transformation of a park.
- NUA supports **evidence-based urban planning and design**. By assessing the mental health profile and needs of residents in a specific area, it provides actionable recommendations for introducing design solutions that are justified and tailored to the specific community's needs.
- The methodology allows for the **comparative analysis of mental wellbeing across different areas**. This can help urban decision-makers identify areas most in need of environmental interventions or, conversely, highlight places that are particularly successful in providing mental health benefits.
- Furthermore, NUA enables continuous **health and wellbeing monitoring over time**. Collecting data across multiple time points can reveal more nuanced fluctuations in wellbeing and the long-term effects of ongoing environmental changes.

Beyond these specific applications, NUA aims to empower various stakeholders, including urban planners, researchers, policymakers, and residents, to integrate mental health considerations into the design and planning of urban spaces. By providing evidence-based, actionable metrics, it supports the creation of urban interventions that foster mentally healthy living environments. This systematic approach helps stakeholders to identify high-impact projects, prioritize interventions, and effectively communicate policy outcomes. A distinguishing feature is also its emphasis on inclusivity, promoting equitable engagement by empowering residents to actively participate in NUA measurement based on their unique relationship with space. NUA

incorporates the methods of in-situ brain activity recording through the portable EEG devices to uncover the way in which the average human brain responds to the surrounding built and natural environment. The built and natural environment affects human mental health and wellbeing through specific urban health determinants.

Research shows that there are multiple factors influencing the state of wellbeing in place (Bonifácio et al., 2023; Lovell et al., 2015; Whitehead & Dahlgren, 1991). Below, Figure 5 presents the summary of the current state of the art in recognising determinants of urban health, which have direct implications for NUA. Any of the determinants can have a negative or positive impact on health in place, depending on the conditions in which a person is found. Thus, they can assume the role of 'urban stressors' or 'urban health promoters'. These determinants can be grouped into five main categories:

1. Global drivers of change,
2. Quality of built environment,
3. Social factors,
4. Lifestyle
5. Socio-demographics.

The first, most holistic category, the *Global drivers of change*, includes the factors that can have a great impact on people's lives but are not contingent on the local context and decision making. Phenomena such as conflicts, pandemics, natural disasters, migrations, climate crises, digital transitions, and similar, fall under this category.

The quality of the built environment is much more influenced by the local decision-making, urban planning and design interventions. Its relationship with urban health is continuously being explored by the new approaches, such as neurourbanism and NUA is predominantly to inform this body of knowledge. Within the quality of urban environment there have been several determinants linked to people's mental health, these include: the availability and accessibility of green and blue spaces (Beute et al., 2020; Beute et al., 2023), including presence and accessibility of green spaces (Lovell et al., 2015), as well as their quality and aesthetics (Olszewska-Guizzo, 2023), among many other environmental factors such as biodiversity, transport and mobility (Mindell & Watkins, 2024), thermal comfort, noise and pollution. More details on these can be found in the section 3.1.3 *Spatial and environmental measures below*.

Figure 5. Determinants of urban health, adapted from (Whitehead & Dahlgren, 1991). Furthermore, the *Social factors*, according to research, can be significant moderators of mental health in place. Aspects such as a sense of community, sense of place, safety, population density & crowdedness can greatly impact how we are feeling in a certain neighbourhood. *Lifestyle* factors, such as physical activity, substance use, sleep habits, eating habits, screen time, and time outdoors are also important to take into account when analysing the relationship between space and health. Lastly, *Socio-demographic factors*, such as age, gender, education, socio-economic status, occupation, and individual health issues are also important and can greatly moderate the way we interact and perceive the living environment.

3.1 NUA Building blocks

The NUA method relies on multiple measures recorded from residents and their living environment. Among these measures, we can distinguish those related to mental health, wellbeing and the perception of space, as well as those related to the behaviour and lifestyle and directly referring to the equality of the built environment.

Some of the NUA metrics are subjective, such as participants' self-reports – they rely on the personal assessments and views of people (opinions), and others are more objective, such as for example noise levels at the neighbourhood square. The following Figure 6 presents all three main groups of measures integrated in the NUA methodology.

Figure 6. Different types of measures integrated into NUA-index.

3.1.1 Objective neuro-physiological measures

Physiological data provide objective measures of how people react to stimuli, reflecting autonomic nervous system activity and cognitive and emotional information processing. Mobile EEG devices measure brain activity as participants move through spaces, offering insights into their states of relaxation, alertness, or engagement. The NUA methodology leverages objective measures of mental health and wellbeing that are in part based in human electrophysiology. These measures aim at recording and capturing the mental state of residents as they are exploring urban spaces, by directly recording the electrical byproduct of their neural and bodily activities. These activities primarily include brain activity oscillations recorded at the participant's scalp. Other measures such as heart rate can provide information of a person's wellbeing.

NUA methodology specifically integrates in-situ neurophysiological measurements, focusing on Electroencephalography (EEG) and Heart Rate (HR). These measures are collected using portable, mobile devices like the Muse 2 headband or similar, which are designed for ease of use in real-world settings. The aim is to capture brain responses and physiological states as participants interact with their actual living environments.

Brain oscillations

For EEG data, NUA's analysis focuses on specific brainwave frequency bands, particularly the **alpha (8–13 Hz)** and **beta (13–30 Hz)** bands. These frequencies are relevant to mental health and wellbeing.

Alpha oscillations are of particular interest here because studies have highlighted a connection between changes in their intensity and behaviour and mental states associated with wellbeing (Segrave et al., 2011). Notably, increasing alpha power captured at the right frontal aspect of the scalp has been linked to a tendency to approach stimuli that are considered positive or relevant to an ongoing goal. Furthermore, greater right frontal alpha power has been linked to tendencies towards positive attitudes and positive emotional experiences, whilst increased left hemispheric alpha activity has been connected to negative emotions, withdrawal tendencies, and experiences of negative attitudes towards a given situation or sensory impression (Davidson, 2004). Together these findings point to alpha oscillation as a key biomarker of wellbeing, and it is leveraged by the present methodology.

Beta oscillations differ in that they oscillate at a higher frequency range between 14 hertz to 30 hertz, typically observed over the temporal lobe at the side of the head. Beta oscillations are relevant to the present methodology because they can be studied to understand attentional engagement of an individual with a specific task or a specific environment.

Together alpha and beta oscillations are key objective measures, and they are integrated in NUA. Thanks to recent technological advancements, it has become increasingly feasible to record these measures accurately, and there are now few challenges to capturing them from residents as they go about their daily life. Furthermore, they are rooted in prior literature, and bridge the gaps between, the environment, attention and cognition and the positive effect of urban environment on wellbeing.

Heart Rate Measures

Concurrently, **Heart Rate (HR)** is measured to provide insights into autonomic nervous system activity. Changes in heart rate can indicate various activation states, including stress.

Heart rate measures are often thought to be straightforward to capture, because they are widespread in consumer products such as sport watches. These products do provide heart rate information, but heart rate changes are not a reliable measure for autonomic nervous system response. This is because they are under the influence of physiological systems that are not related to stress, such as physical activity, breathing, digestive processes and hormonal influences. In contrast, heart rate variability (HRV) is not influenced by these physiological processes (Baevsky & Chernikova, 2017). HRV captures how much heart rate changes from moment to moment. It responds to

autonomous system activation by a decrease in value and as such is an established measure of stress, especially prolonged stress (Thayer et al., 2012).

By collecting HR data simultaneously with EEG, NUA gains a more comprehensive picture of a participant's physiological response to their environment, capturing both brain activity patterns and general arousal/stress levels.

3.1.2. Subjective, self-reported measures

Self-reported measures are tools or instruments through which individuals provide direct insights into their thoughts, emotions, behaviours, or experiences, typically through questionnaires, interviews, or rating scales. These measures rely on the assumption that individuals are both aware of and capable of accurately communicating their internal states or actions, offering a **subjective** perspective that can be complemented by objective or observational methods in understanding different psychological phenomena. In NUA through **self-reported questionnaires**, participants report their subjective judgements towards their individual experience as well as the experience of the spaces they live in.

While not directly enabling the *technical* assignment of alpha power data to a location (no GPS tracking), self-reported approaches like mental mapping play a crucial complementary role in NUA's co-analysis phase. Mental mapping exercise captures residents' subjective insights into their neighbourhood, allowing them to identify perceived stress-inducing and calming environments. By collecting subjective spatial information (mental maps) alongside the objective neurophysiological data, NUA facilitates a richer understanding of the human-environment interaction. This allows NUA to understand how physiological states, such as relaxation indicated by alpha power, are potentially associated with specific areas identified subjectively by residents as calming or beneficial.

In NUA, subjective measures play a pivotal role in supporting the findings from physiological assessments guiding individuals' perceptions, emotions, and wellbeing across various dimensions. These tools are well-established in the field and are commonly used in similar ongoing studies and like approaches, providing valuable insights into participants' mental health, life satisfaction, stress levels, and other psychosocial factors. In Table 5 below, we present key subjective measures utilized in our study, with a focus on their purpose, practical applications, and significance. The actual questionnaires can be found in **Annex 1 and 2**.

Table 5. Self-reported questionnaires integrated in NUA

	Instrument (item code)	Scope	Number of Items	Scale	Administration Time	Literature Reference	Remarks
1	Generalised Anxiety Disorder, GAD-7 (GA)	Severity of generalized anxiety disorder (GAD) symptoms (e.g., worry, restlessness)	7	4-point scale (0 = "Not at all" to 3 = "Nearly every day")	2-3 minutes	(Spitzer et al., 2006)	Self-administered, widely used in clinical and research settings
2	Patient Health Questionnaire, PHQ-8	Severity of depressive symptoms (e.g., anhedonia, fatigue, sleep disturbances)	8	4-point scale (0 = "Not at all" to 3 = "Nearly every day")	2-3 minutes	(Kroenke et al., 2009)	Derived from PHQ-9 (omits suicide item), used in epidemiological studies
3	Perceived Stress Scale, PSS-10 (PS)	Perceived stress (feelings of unpredictability, uncontrollability, overload)	10	5-point Likert scale (0 = "Never" to 4 = "Very often")	~5 minutes	(Cohen et al., 1983)	Measures stress over the past month, widely used in mental health research
4	World Health Organization Quality of Life, WHOQOL- BREF (WH)	Quality of life across four domains: physical, psychological, social, environmental. Basic demographics (age, gender, education).	29	5-point Likert scale (varies by item, e.g., intensity, frequency)	10-15 minutes	WHOqolGroup (1998)	Abbreviated from WHOQOL-100, cross-culturally validated
5	Brief Sense of Community Scale (BC)	Sense of belonging and connection within a community	8	5-point Likert scale (1="Strongly Agree" to 5="Strongly Disagree")	~3-5 minutes	(Peterson et al., 2008)	Often used in urban and social psychology studies.
6	Screentime & Playtime Outdoors (ST)	Self-reported digital media use and outdoor activity levels	5	Likert, frequency, or duration-based	~2-3 minutes	Adapted from	Custom-designed for specific studies based on previous epidemiological research

	Instrument (item code)	Scope	Number of Items	Scale	Administration Time	Literature Reference	Remarks
						(Bernard et al., 2017)	
7	Sociodemographic & Self-Developed Questions (NP, SD, HL)	Background (income, education, postal code, neighborhood perception, health, lifestyle).	19	Mixed (categorical, Likert, open-ended)	5-7 minutes	(NUA-specific)	Custom-designed for the NUA study, contextualizes wellbeing in relation to living environment
8	Daily Mood Questionnaires*	Fluctuations in mood states (e.g., happiness, anxiety, energy)	Varies (often 5-10)	Likert or visual analog scales (VAS)	~1-2 minutes per day	(NUA-specific)	Often used in ecological momentary assessment (EMA) studies
9	Post-Recording Questions*	Experiences during EEG recording (e.g., place of recording, activities, technical difficulties)	Varies (custom)	Likert or open-ended	~2-5 minutes after recording session	(NUA-specific)	Tailored to study design (e.g., after exposure to nature, media, etc.)
10	Mental map	Drawing the walking path with marked experiences and observations during the site exposure	1	(no scale)	2-3 minutes	(NUA-specific)	At the end of the protocol, while dropping off the device.

Notes: * short digital questionnaires sent to participants after the enrolment meeting during 5 days of protocol.

These subjective measures were selected with a focus on depression and anxiety, two of the most pressing mental health concerns in Europe today. Research indicates that these issues are prevalent across many European neighbourhoods, making them critical areas of investigation. Additionally, the study incorporates measures that can be influenced by the living environment, such as sleep quality and screen time, which may act as moderators of individuals' behaviours and interactions with their surroundings. By exploring these dimensions, the NUA study aims to deepen our understanding of how mental health and wellbeing are shaped by both personal and environmental factors.

3.1.3 Spatial and environmental measures

Spatial-environmental measures included in NUA are based on the current knowledge of the built environment characteristics influencing human mental health and wellbeing. To come up with the meaningful results NUA must objectively assess the site-specific qualities that could have potential impact on residents' mental health and wellbeing. Environmental characteristics determining the urban health and mental health specifically are by their nature, in constant flow, however NUA attempts to be as objective as possible to allow the comparative analysis between different sites. Spatial and environmental measures for NUA exclude the self-reported, subjective measures linked to the perception of the neighbourhood and focus on more technical measurement of the living environment, applicable to any site using the same measurement instruments. For NUA only the spatial and environmental metrics, which, based on previous scientific research, were associated with mental health and wellbeing at the neighbourhood scale, were included, and presented in the Table 6.

Table 6. Environmental measurements in NUA

	Urban health determinant	Lit. references, linking with mental health benefits	Data source	Measurement tool /NUA item(s)
1	Canopy cover area	(Juengst et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2022)	EA	%
2	Permeable surface ratio	(Bjørndal et al., 2024; Li et al., 2018)	EA	%
3	Specific NbS from the GreenInCities preliminary Catalogue of Solutions,	GreenInCities-specific	GIC	(Y/N – integrate all catalogue of NbS)
4	Noise	(Mucci et al., 2020)	EA	dB
5	Thermal comfort	(Abdel-Ghany et al., 2013; Gillerot et al., 2024; Meidenbauer et al., 2024)	EA	Thom's discomfort index (Stathopoulou et al., 2005)
6	Air quality	(Lu, 2020)	OD	µg/m ³ NO ₂ , µg/m ³ CO,

				µg/m ³ PM _{2.5}
7	Landscape visual quality and features/ urban morphology, topography, composition and aesthetics.	Contemplative Landscape Model (CLM) (Olszewska-Guizzo, Sia, et al., 2022)	EA	CLM score (Olszewska-Guizzo et al., 2023)

Notes: GIC-GreenInCities-specific catalogue, EA – Expert Assessment, OD – online databases.

There could be multiple examples of the mechanisms of how the listed environmental characteristics impact mental health and wellbeing of urban residents. For example, planting more street trees is a specific urban intervention that can improve noise shielding which in turn reduces the urban noise. NUA could measure the change in noise levels objectively using an environment meter and associate it with recorded participants' neurophysiological responses (like brain activity via mEEG) and self-reported stress levels before and after the intervention. This would provide evidence on the tangible benefits (e.g., reduced noise leading to reduced stress) resulting from this very specific intervention. Similarly, introducing more natural topography could be assessed through the expert-based visual landscape quality assessment – Contemplative Landscape Model (CLM). NUA could assess changes in perceived stress, anxiety, or mood in areas with varied topography, correlating these with the objective topographical data captured through spatial measures and potentially neurophysiological responses reflecting states like relaxation or alertness. These examples highlight how NUA integrates objective spatial-environmental data with physiological and self-report measures to understand the impact of urban interventions on mental health at the neighbourhood scale. Aiming at linking specific characteristics of the built and natural environment to observable mental health and wellbeing outcomes.

Finally, it is important to note that all environmental measurements need to be collected within the area of interest, underlining the importance of a clear site boundary (see the following section 3.2 *Site Eligibility Criteria*).

3.2 Site Eligibility Criteria

Neurourbanism Assessment methodology is designed with broad applicability in mind, allowing for its implementation across a wide range of geographic and demographic settings. A primary consideration for site eligibility is the ability to conduct the assessment in any country worldwide, encompassing both urban and rural settlements. This global reach ensures the methodology can be applied wherever people reside. However, while the potential scope is vast, practical constraints related to logistics, equipment safety, and researcher security must be carefully evaluated. For instance, conducting the NUA would be inadvisable in high-risk areas such as active conflict zones or regions with significant safety concerns.

One important step for ensuring the proper application of NUA is spatial scale or unit for analysis. As NUA is mainly concerned with experience of people in an urban environment, which means it is necessary to have a spatial unit that is not only familiar for the citizen scientist or subject, but that this is shared by most of them, i.e., it is in a cognitive space of their shared mental maps. This can be approached from an urban planning perspective - with the neighbourhood unit concept and its evolution – or from an urban sociology perspective – with various concepts relating to the spatial turn in sociology. Most recently however, for the purposes of the European projects the neighbourhood is defined in simplified terms, as an area that either has a maximum of 25 km² or a maximum of 10,000 inhabitants. A neighbourhood should also be part of or represent the lowest level of a public administration or elected body such as a quarter, borough or district⁹ (see also 1.9 Central Concepts).

The original **neighbourhood unit concept** was centred around safe walking to schools, no longer than 400-800 meters walk from the residential area. Moreover, the area itself would not exceed 5000-9000 residents - required to fill up the seats in the school (see Figure 7, and (Perry, 2004)). While this was later used as the most influential planning tool in the West, the micro district emerged as a soviet counterpart, limiting residential spatial units in no more than 80 hectares, to be bounded by natural, green elements or arterial roads, and no more than 500-metre distance of any residential unit from public services (Pallot & Shaw, 2021). As a planning tool, the neighbourhood unit was criticised for fuelling segregation and urban sprawl in the United States (Freeman, 2001; Silver, 1985).

⁹https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2025/wp-13-new-european-bauhaus-facility_horizon-2025_en.pdf

Figure 7. Neighborhood unit components (Image credit: Perry, 2004)

From the perspective of the concept of NUA, we focus on whether this concept can be used as a spatial unit for neourbanism assessment, rather than as a planning instrument, or a morally questionable tool to influence social relationships.

The sociological correlation to the concept neighbourhood unit was the “primary group theory”, in which social relationships are formed through interactions within one’s primary groups, such as family, play groups, and the neighbourhood (Cooley, 2001). As this was a main influence on Perry’s neighbourhood unit, it translated to a promotion of spaces of interaction in the unit, such as churches, parks, community centres. However, this does not describe a deterministic relationship between environmental features and the social outcomes, but rather a possibilistic, or at most a probabilistic one (Patricios, 2002). There have also been numerous cases historically where this promotion of social interaction was out of touch from the reality of the communities on the ground (Banerjee & Baer, 2013). In contemporary communities, there are also significant forces of social isolation in spatial units, such as digitalization, gentrification, or becoming more car-dependent (Freeman, 2001). The New Urbanism movement, a natural successor to the neighbourhood unit, offers some remedies to this by prescribing affordable housing, compact, walkable cities with a diversity of functions, and an adjustment of street network to offer more internal connectivity (Kim & Kaplan, 2004).

In the social sciences, several influential concepts help define spatial units of social groups and communities. These frameworks explore how space and place shape – and

are shaped by – social relationships, identities, and power structures. In the *Production of Space*, Lefebvre describes spatial practice and representational space, encompassing routines, interactions, use of space, navigation (spatial practice), and meanings, emotions, symbols in a spatial aggregate (representational space) (Lefebvre & Nicholson-Smith, 1991). In this sense, space is a social product, constructed through human relations. The spatial unit in this sense is delimited by the extent of being shared by members of a self-recognizing community. This rhymes with the concept of the **sociotope**, which, akin to the biotope, is a spatial unit characterized by shared social meaning and practices (Stähle, 2013), or spatial communities, which refers to certain places constructing communities from co-presence and co-use, such as common spaces, workplaces, or third places (Heiskanen, 2012). A sociological approach would reject the idea of standardized spatial units, as different cultures and different social relations, would produce different spaces. However, there is a limitation to this approach, as contemporary cities are less characterized by organic social production, as a mix of expressions of power, planning, deterritorialization of spaces with information, communication, and transportation systems tend to liquidate these „spaces of places“ into „spaces of flows“, which is more graspable by networks rather than territories (Castells, 1999).

In conclusion, we propose three approaches to define a spatial unit for NUA assessment:

1. **Neighbourhood unit approach** - the higher fidelity approach would mean defining the unit by the people: deploying a mapping technique (e.g., mental mapping or sociotope mapping) to identify to what spatial extent there are a widely shared meaning and widely shared spatial practices (use of space, mobile practices, social interactions). This approach is recommended in case it is feasible, and in case the area of interest can be understood as a space of places, rather than as a space of flows. Residential areas, traditional urban centres, or pre-industrial settlements in general, and campus-like sites are typical examples for spaces of places. In the case of the physical fabric changing relatively rarely as compared to the social fabric – e.g., due to a flux of immigration – a sociological approach is necessary, as physical indicators of a neighbourhood are less reliable.
2. **Sociological approach** - In contrast, if the social composition has largely followed or integrated to the physical context, and it is not feasible to conduct this mapping exercise, it is possible to define the unit by its physical characteristics: in the European context, one could look for physical indicators: a unit that is walkable, with primary, everyday services at the centre (meaning parks, kindergartens, churches, general practitioners, community centres, not commercial services), the presence of third places that could host social

interactions, distinct symbols, architectural style, and a streetscape supporting internal connectivity rather than thoroughfare.

- Finally, if the area of interest centres around spaces of flows, then their **deterritorialization** effect means that no such spatial unit can be constructed, unless it is done so in topological space.

Table 8. Summary guide to select spatial unit for NUA assessment

	1 Neighbourhood unit approach	2 Sociological approach	3 Deterritorialization
Spaces of places (e.g. residential neighbourhood, university campus)	x	x	
Spaces of flows (e.g. social media, train station)			x
High cultural diversity or resident turnover		x	
Low cultural diversity and resident turnover	x	x	

3.3 Participant Recruitment

The foundation of NUA's scientific integrity and social impact rests on the recruitment strategy, as it serves several critical functions. To this end, NUA's recruitment main pillars are equity and inclusion. Recruiting a diverse and representative cross-section of each neighbourhood ensures that the findings are grounded in the lived experiences of all community members, including those who are often underrepresented in research. In turn, this enhances the relevance and impact of the findings for local communities. We focus on three key demographic characteristics relevant to each site, typically including age distribution, socioeconomic status and education level. Depending on the specific context of each neighbourhood, other characteristics such as ethnicity or gender may be prioritised instead. The aim is to consistently select a set of at least three priority characteristics that best capture the diversity and lived experiences of the neighbourhood's residents.

Second, the success of the methodology relies on the sustained and active involvement of residents throughout the study's process. This means recognising that residents bring different motivations, expectations, and levels of engagement to their participation. NUA's recruitment strategy acknowledges that people participate for many reasons

beyond altruism or financial incentives. Individuals driven by social and value-based incentives like a sense of contribution to science and neighbourhood improvement, the social experience of engaging in something with friends or family and the opportunity for self-exploration are then more likely to remain actively engaged (McDougle et al., 2011). Nevertheless, material incentives, such as the voucher offered at the end of the study, serve as important enablers of participation. Particularly, they signal that participants' time and contributions is acknowledged and valued, promoting sustained engagement and a more equitable relationship with researchers.

Third, by addressing these motivations within its recruitment strategy, NUA also contributes to participants' own learning, self-awareness, and community connectedness. This is at the heart of a citizen science approach, in which participants are empowered to shape the research process, reflecting on their own mental wellbeing and learning how to collect their own neurophysiological data in high quality (see more in 2.3.4 NUA - a Citizen's Science Approach).

3.3.1 Meeting participants where they are: recruitment strategies

NUA's recruitment strategy is intentionally designed to be multi-faceted, comprehensive and adaptive for each city. It employs both well-established, evidence-based recruitment procedures from psychology and the social sciences, as well as more novel, community-oriented engagement methods that are seldom applied in conventional mental health or scientific research. In the sections that follow, we discuss each of these approaches, including their underlying rationale, important steps in implementation, and respective strengths and limitations. Examples and insights from the first NUA testing period that took place in Nova Gorica, Slovenia will be used to highlight ways in which our strategy was tailored and employed. This overview is intended to guide the flexible and integrated use of these strategies, enabling NUA to effectively engage a wide range of urban neighbourhoods and population groups.

Flyers and posters

One of the more traditional recruitment methods used in psychology and community-based research is the distribution of paper-based recruitment material which serve as passive awareness tools. Flyers and posters can be placed in many locations within the neighbourhood, including libraries, local stores, places of worship and universities. Further, certain locations or community "hubs" within neighbourhoods can also be selected to target specific populations (e.g., retirees). Flyers may appeal to individuals who are less digitally connected or prefer to engage at their own pace. They also help build legitimacy through visible presence in trusted public spaces. Additionally, this method may attract participants who are motivated by general curiosity, and their interest via this route highlights self-directed engagement.

Strengths: Low cost, broad coverage, quick implementation, inclusive of less tech-inclined individuals.

Limitations: No participant-researcher interaction which limits the opportunity for building trust and may result in low recruitment yield.

In person, on-site recruitment

Another traditional strategy from social science and citizen science research involves actively engaging participants in person to communicate the opportunity to participate in NUA and record interest. Members of the NUA team visit places of high traffic, typically on the street, the entrance of key locations or at the site of data collection, distributing flyers and answering questions and concerns. In-person engagement formed the core of the Nova Gorica strategy, especially in Koren Park during weekends and late afternoons (outside working hours) or in public spaces such as the library (see Figure 8). Team members approach residents directly, introduce the project, and follow up with a text to schedule data collection sessions. The priority is explaining the importance of the project to attract participants who are motivated to contribute towards neighbourhood improvement. This strategy is deeply relational. It allows the project to be explained clearly, concerns to be addressed in real time, and trust to be established. In line with citizen science principles (West & Pateman, 2016), this strategy exemplifies mutual engagement and co-presence.

Figure 8. On-site recruitment of the local residents, at the public library, Nova Gorica, April 2025.

Strengths: Easy implementation, inclusive of less tech-inclined individuals, useful to raise awareness about NUA, offers opportunities for engagement with participants, trust and relationship building.

Limitations: Costly in resources as it requires involvement of team members, challenging to scale up, challenging to engage communities with diverse languages.

Word-of-mouth

This strategy, most common in psychology and marketing research, leverages the social influence and local network of participants. Residents who participate are encouraged to share information about the NUA and bring friends and family along in data collection sessions— a form of social diffusion particularly effective in tight-knit communities. This strategy targets individuals who are motivated to share their participation experience with friends/family and is particularly effective in reaching individuals who may not have been receptive to other more institutional outreach strategies. Familiar contacts don't need to earn credibility, making the NUA project feel more accessible and less intimidating. Additionally, it is often the case that referred individuals have had informal learning through peer explanations, limiting the time spent with the researcher.

Strengths: Requires little resources, helps in establishing trust, scales up naturally as the number of participants increases, inclusive of less tech-inclined individuals, useful in raising awareness about the NUA within communities and in recruiting groups speaking diverse languages and dialects.

Limitations: The strategy's strength depends heavily on early participants having a positive experience. A poorly executed early data collection session may have the opposite effect. The efficacy is also dependent on participants' motivations and recruitment may become limited to families and communities that have already participated and exclude others, if left unchecked.

Social media and Digital platforms

A more recent dynamic tool in recruiting participants for social science research involves employing a marketing framework by using social media to increase representativeness within samples (Howcutt et al., 2018). Tailored and engaging content relative to NUA, such as videos, interactive FAQs and blogs, is created and shared on social media platforms like Instagram, Facebook and WhatsApp (example in Figure 9). When used effectively, these platforms can reach a wide demographic, especially younger participants in different online communities (e.g., posting within selected Facebook groups for targeted outreach).

Figure 9. Instagram posts about the NUA in Nova Gorica, inviting residents to participate.

This strategy also involves framing the study to better match the motivations and interests of a particular online community. For example, promoting NUA as an urban wellbeing exploration, as well as tailoring the aesthetic and language of posts may increase attractiveness for certain individuals or community identities. Usually, this approach aligns best with participants who are motivated to learn, become part of something innovative to help scientific progression and have an active online presence.

Strengths: Tailored to target underrepresented demographics increasing diversity, plays a critical role in retaining participants' engagement, reinforces commitment and invites continued involvement (from T1 to T2).

Limitations: Low recruitment yield in cities with low online presence (e.g., Nova Gorica). The content generated must be culturally and linguistically tuned so not to be impersonal and easily overlooked. This makes it resource intensive requiring regular monitoring of channels, a consistent narrative and constant engagement.

Local Media (press releases)

A less traditional strategy in recruiting participants for social science research, but vital for spreading awareness about the NUA, involves collaborations with local media such as newspapers and radio stations. Local media can reach residents in their everyday routines, establishing credibility by framing NUA as something meaningful, endorsed and happening in the neighbourhood.

Strengths: Can reach a wide but local audience, especially individuals with limited online presence. It helps address scepticism about the study by showing that it is respected and supported by local institutions.

Limitations: Local media is subject to scheduling and editorial priorities making media-dependent timelines hard to control and misaligned with data collection windows. Language barriers may also arise, requiring high quality translation and aid from local partners to prevent miscommunication.

Workshop based engagement

Mostly used in community-based and citizen science research, workshop-based engagement represents a strategy that combines recruitment with education and co-learning. Workshops offer a welcoming space to demystify the project, explain the equipment used, and highlight the self-reflective and scientific aspects of participation. Such events are especially attractive to participants motivated by a desire to learn, meet others, or better understand mental health in urban contexts.

Strengths: Supports longer-term engagement by building familiarity with NUA team members, serves as onboarding platforms and limits time spent training and explaining procedures during data collection sessions and enhances citizen science approach in NUA.

Limitations: Time consuming and costly in terms of resources as team members must plan, organise and carry out the workshops in tandem of preparing data collection sessions.

Gatekeeper and community engagement

A recruitment strategy that is especially important for accessing hard-to-reach populations is researchers engaging gatekeepers (Todowede et al., 2023). These are respected figures that hold access to organisations or institutions such as religious leaders, teachers or neighbourhood coordinators, providing a subtle but powerful method of building trust. Gatekeepers' support functions as a form of endorsement, opening doors to populations who might otherwise feel excluded or unsure, connecting NUA to established community networks. Gatekeeper engagement is especially useful for reaching unemployed youth, ethnic minorities, or older residents, as noted by (Unell & Castle, 2012).

Strengths: Shown to help in recruiting diverse populations, fosters deeper inclusion by reducing social distance between researchers and residents, reinforces the perception that NUA is a community-relevant initiative and establishes trust.

Limitations: Dependent on gatekeepers' priorities, bias and support, and inadvertent framing of project in ways that misrepresent NUA goals and time commitment.

Local government and University support

Support from cities' municipalities and universities lent NUA institutional credibility. Formal partnerships help communicate that the project has local relevance and is in alignment with broader goals for public wellbeing and urban improvement. This strategy primarily appeals to participants driven by civic or value-based motivations, such as being part of something meaningful or helping their city.

Strengths: Increases credibility and visibility, boosts recruitment efficiency by enhancing reach by using official channels of communication and engages local community.

Limitations: Dependent on local partners' priorities, resources and procedures which may delay participant recruitment. Additionally, some residents may be reluctant to

engage with initiatives endorsed by local authorities due to lack of trust in government institutions. This may especially affect recruitment of marginalised or historically underserved groups who might perceive institutional backing as politically driven or detached from community needs.

Figure 10. The resident's journey from the NUA data collection.

Eligibility Criteria

To ensure scientific validity and consistency of neurophysiological data collected across cities, NUA applies specific eligibility criteria for participation. Participants must be adults (18+), without a current or past neurological or psychiatric diagnosis. This is justified by two core considerations:

Scientific Validity: Neurophysiological data (e.g., EEG) are sensitive to internal mental and neurological states. Including participants with clinical diagnoses would introduce uncontrolled variance preventing us from isolating and observing the effects of environmental stimuli on brain activity. The inclusion of only participants without neurological or psychiatric diagnoses allows for a more accurate interpretation of results.

Ethical Responsibility: As the project is not a clinical study, we are unable to offer clinical support. Including vulnerable individuals without clinical oversight would pose ethical risks, especially with regards to potential unintentional stress arising during data collection. Additionally, participants are invited to reflect on their own wellbeing and learn about collecting neurophysiological data, as part of the citizen science approach. This process is more ethically sound when individuals are less likely to misinterpret this experience as diagnosis or therapy.

Furthermore, whilst the goal is for children and adolescents to also be included in future iterations of the project, this population requires tailored procedures and ethical approvals; hence they were excluded in the current phase. However, our focus and

priority are to include as many age groups in the adult population as possible to collect a representative sample.

Finally, only right-handed individuals are eligible for participation. This criterion is based on well-established neurophysiological research supporting that brain lateralisation differs between right- and left-handed individuals (Papadatou-Pastou et al., 2020). Limiting participation to right-handed helps ensure that observed differences are related to environmental factors rather than individual neurological variability linked to handedness.

Sample Size

We aim to recruit a minimum of **50 individuals** for each urban neighbourhood under study. This target sample size is meticulously chosen to ensure the robustness and representativeness of findings at the neighbourhood scale. This can be approached through the NUA foundation on the "diagnosis of the space", seeking to understand how the human brain responds to its surroundings, with the goal of optimizing these environments for mental health promotion. This distinguishes it from traditional clinical assessments that primarily focus on individual diagnoses. Therefore, representativeness is not solely about individual clinical outcomes but about capturing the *collective human experience* within a defined urban spatial unit. This can be a "neighbourhood unit," historically designed to accommodate 5,000-9,000 residents, or a sociological "socio-type" characterized by shared social meaning and practices. The sample size should then adequately reflect the characteristics of residents within these carefully defined areas, prioritizing the everyday users of the space.

This sample size is further informed by statistical power considerations necessary to observe the statistically significant differences between measurements. According to G*Power conducted¹⁰, a total required sample size should be a minimum of 36 participants. However, NUA aims for a higher target of 50 participants because of the following considerations:

- Mitigation of Participant Drop-out: Recruiting above the statistical minimum directly addresses the practical challenge of potential participant drop-out that can occur between data collection timepoints, such as residents relocating or withdrawing from the study. This ensures that sufficient data remains for robust analysis, especially for longitudinal designs assessing pre- and post-intervention impacts
- Enhanced Representativeness and Inclusivity: A larger sample size further enhances the ability to capture the diverse socio-economic and socio-demographic characteristics prevalent in heterogeneous urban neighborhoods. This proactive approach moves beyond concerns about

¹⁰ F-test ANOVA: Repeated measures, within factors, a design suitable for detecting changes in mental wellbeing metrics over time. With an effect size (f) of 0.25, an alpha error probability (alpha err. prob) of 0.05, and a desired power (1-beta err prob) of 0.95, for one group and four measurements (e.g., multiple assessment timepoints or different environmental exposures), with a correlation among repeated measures of 0.5 and a nonsphericity correction (epsilon) of 1 (G*Power, Version 3.1.9.7).

non-representative, "WEIRD" samples often seen in traditional neuroscience research, thereby strengthening the ecological validity and generalizability of NUA's findings to the actual users of urban spaces. This directly supports the citizen science approach by fostering broader community engagement and ownership of mental health outcomes.

- Increased Statistical Power and Precision: Recruiting more participants than the statistical minimum allows for the detection of more subtle effects of urban interventions on mental wellbeing and provides more precise estimates of variability within the population. This strengthens the reliability of the NUA Index and its ability to discern meaningful changes over time or between different urban contexts. Furthermore, it provides more room to account for individual differences in advanced statistical models, which can refine estimates and enhance comparability across neighborhoods.

Recruitment Timeline and Seasonality

The timing of recruitment is critical to the internal validity of the NUA methodology. Urban lifestyle and experience, as well as mental wellbeing are sensitive to seasonal variation. Hence, data collection and recruitment are time-bounded, ideally unfolding within a single season. This approach avoids confounding influences such as changes in daylight, temperature and vegetation or reported seasonal variability in human psychology (Hohm et al., 2024). Therefore, recruitment should ideally be launched at the beginning of a season and the data collection period should take place at the end of the season. This would provide at least a month or two of lead time for raising awareness, especially via online outreach and local contact participatory activities, initiating gatekeeper engagement and building a pipeline of participants that encourages a more intensive and efficient data collection period.

3.3.2 Tailoring Recruitment for each City

The NUA recruitment strategy is very site-specific and should be tailored for each city by combining the approaches that are relevant to optimise recruitment and adapting them to local contexts. As an example for the NUA testing period in Nova Gorica, (Slovenia), our recruitment strategy was adapted by:

- Structuring in-person recruitment by identifying local activities and events (high-traffic locations) occurring during the data collection period, like Nova Gorica's European Cultural Capital events,
- Focusing on age distribution, socioeconomic status and gender in terms of demographic characteristics,
- Identifying the most effective in-person outreach spots (e.g., local library and Koren park) and allocating more time and resources to those locations,
- Preparing flyers and posters, translating and disseminating them with the help of local partners,
- Identifying low online presence and prioritising other means of recruitment,

- Forging collaboration with a local radio station (Radio Robin), preparing a press-release and translating it with the help of local partners,
- Encouraging word-of-mouth by scheduling data collection sessions with participants' friends and family,
- Visiting the retiree community's local hub and attempting to recruit older residents with the help of a local translator,
- Harnessing the support of local partners (the municipality of Nova Gorica and the University of Nova Gorica),
- Understanding the residents' attitudes and motivations to participate (i.e., being attracted to the feeling that the data collection process was simple and that they could contribute without difficulty)
- Keeping open lines of communication with individuals interested in participating via WhatsApp.

Below in Table 9 we outline the level of contribution of each recruitment strategy implemented in Nova Gorica in the final sample size. The percentage of recruited samples, ranks the relative effectiveness of each strategy in terms of volume (recruitment yield), calculated by dividing the number of participants recruited via a certain strategy by the total number of recruited participants.

Table 9. Recruitment strategies and their yield in participants.

Recruitment Strategy	Tested in Nova Gorica	Recruitment yield	% of recruited sample	Notes
University contacts	✓	Very high yield	42%	Provided student participants living in Koren; aided by University of Nova Gorica.
Word-of-mouth	✓	High yield	20%	Many participants brought friends/family members.
Municipality contacts	✓	High yield	20%	Provided contacts and credibility.
In-person in public spaces (site + library)	✓	Moderate yield	16%	Primary source of participants; approached in person during weekends and afternoons (outside working hours).
Flyers and posters	✓	Low yield	2%	Visible presence but passive; generated 3 email contacts and only 1 participant completing the study.
In-person at local malls (with translator)	✓	Very low yield	0%	Low engagement: residents rushed or uninterested, despite this being a high-traffic location
Online outreach	✓	Very low yield	0%	Generated awareness (likes and clicks) via targeted posts on Instagram and Facebook but no contacts. Online

				communities across social media channels were mostly inactive.
Local media	✓	Very low yield	0%	Promoted the study via local radio during the data collection period; generated no contacts.
Gatekeeper and community engagement	✗	n.a.	n.a	Not applicable.
Workshops	✗	n.a	n.a	Not organised due to limited time and resources.

3.3.2 Protecting the research participants: safety and ethics

Ensuring safety, privacy and rights of all participants is a core commitment of the NUA Methodology. Given the project’s collection of sensitive psychological and physiological data, NUA strictly adheres to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) as per Horizon Europe’s ethics standards. Additionally, the NUA protocol has been approved by The University of Nova Gorica’s ethics committee, as per research regulation standards, emphasising ethical oversight.

Safety and ethics communication: speaking the participants languages

Participation in NUA is strictly voluntary and based on informed consent. Before any data is collected, individuals receive a clear and accessible explanation of the study’s methods and purpose, types of data, and their right to withdraw at any time without consequences. Consent forms and information sheets are provided in local language(s) and explained in person. Importantly, local translators are involved where local barriers exist to ensure that participants fully understand what they are consenting to do to enhance their informed agency. Further, aside from the linguistic component, communication with participants undergoes cultural tailoring, working closely with local partners and gatekeepers to adapt both written and oral materials to context-specific notions of privacy and trust.

All data collection sessions are designed to be as brief as possible and have participants’ comfort as the guiding principle. This means that field work is planned to avoid environmental extremes (e.g., excessive cold), and researchers consistently check on participants’ discomfort during equipment use and throughout the data collection session. No deception, intrusive questioning or distressing content is used at any point during the study.

Empowering participants around their data use and care

NUA takes a participant-centred approach to data ethics, encouraging participants to view themselves as co-owners of the knowledge generated. To achieve this, we focus

on being transparent about data usage and communicating participants' data rights, explaining not only what data is collected, but also why these data matter. We explain how neurophysiological data relate to stress, attention and environmental perception, and emphasise that no individual diagnosis or evaluation is being made. Further, we focus on demystifying the data collection process by showcasing how EEG devices work in a jargon-free and clear way, treating participants as active agents in the research process. Importantly, participants are consistently prompted to ask questions, voice opinions, discuss thoughts and concerns throughout recruitment and data collection phases. This emphasises NUA's commitment to democratising knowledge and reducing power asymmetries that may arise in research.

3.4 Data collection

3.4.1 Protocol overview

This first section presents a brief overview of the NUA protocol. The key aspects of the protocol are presented in Figure 11. A single assessment is performed over seven days and captures mental health and wellbeing measures of the participating residents at one time point and location. The assessment can be repeated after an intervention or change in the environment to measure the impact of the change on residents' wellbeing as per the NUA framework. Whether for a first or second assessment, the structure will stay the same.

The first day of the assessment is an enrollment day. Participants are met at the site, give informed consent, register formally, are trained to record data, and the objective neurophysiological measures are captured while participants explore the site (this step can be skipped though in the case of more certainty about the quality of data recorded by participants), together with self-report measures recorded afterwards. This first meeting lasts about one hour to one hour and a half, and at the end of the meeting the participants go home with the EEG recording device and instructions on how to perform the assessment on their own.

Figure 11. NUA participants signing consent forms, during the enrolment meeting, April 2025, Nova Gorica, Slovenia.

The enrollment meeting is followed by five days during which residents collect the data on their own with the rented devices. Two sets of data are recorded by the participants. The first set is the self-report data. Participants must fill in questionnaires daily that capture their short-term emotional state and wellbeing variable (such as sleep) as well as notable daily events. The second set are EEG and HR recordings using the device. They must perform three recording sessions on their own. One recording is identical to the one that was performed on the site on enrolment day, with the exception that the participant now performs it autonomously. The two other recordings are also performed autonomously but within the participant's home while they engage in daily activities. For each of these recordings, participants must first record a 1-minute rest period, followed by a 20-minute activity period during which they can perform some prescribed activities. After each recording has ended, participants receive a post-recording questionnaire that captures their short-term mood and details about the environment where the recording was performed.

At the end of these five days of assessment, the participants meet researchers again for the final day (Figure 12). This can be at the site or another location. Participants return the device, receive any incentives, fill in complementary reports about their experience and the way they explored the site, as well as receive an invitation to participate in a further campaign assessment if one is planned.

If another campaign of assessment is later performed, for instance for comparison after an intervention on the site, the steps for the new assessment are identical with the exception that participants do not have to give consent or register again. The task structure and participant involvement remain the same.

Figure 12. NUA protocol overview. Steps for post-intervention (T2) assessment are identical, except for administrative steps marked (T1) which are only conducted at the first assessment before intervention.

The step-by-step procedure presenting the steps necessary for the realization of the assessment can be found in **Annex 5**, whilst all materials (e.g., questionnaires and participant guide) used can be found in **Annex 1, 2, 3 and 4**. These steps occur at the location of the assessment, with the participant present. They take about 1 hour to 1.5 hours for each participant under typical conditions.

3.5. Data analysis

After the data collection campaign ends, the data recorded needs to be prepared for conducting analysis to derive reliable and robust results of the assessment. The technical steps for preparing and statistically analysing the data in use are found in detail in **Annex 6**. The following section provides a lay summary of these steps. They may be formed by trained data analysts, or by data analysis systems that may be automated.

3.5.1 Preparing Physiological and Self-Report Data for Use

Physiological Data

EEG recordings are exported and converted into standardised formats to ensure compatibility with analysis tools. Data then undergoes rigorous preprocessing steps to remove any unwanted "noise", such as eye movements, muscle movement that could distort the signals. This cleaning process turns the focus on the brain-related information most relevant to the goals of the assessment.

Cleaned data are divided into smaller time segments and analysed to measure how active the brain is in different frequency ranges, particularly Alpha and Beta waves that are known to be linked to mental states such as calmness, focus, or stress. When possible, we also compare these patterns to each participant's baseline, to better understand how their responses change across environments.

Self-Report Data

Questionnaire responses digitised (e.g., entered in excel) and checked to make sure everything is complete and consistent. Scores are calculated according to the rules of each questionnaire, and any unusual or missing answers are flagged for review. This ensures that the data reflects participants' true responses as reliably as possible.

Statistical Analysis

Processed EEG and self-report data analysed to identify meaningful patterns. Averages and ranges are calculated to understand how participants responded as a group, and how much individual responses varied. Results can be compared across different sites and timepoints, taking demographic information such as age or background into account to interpret findings more accurately and detect subtle effects.

4. NUA Outputs

The NUA is designed to provide meaningful, evidence-based insights into the impact of urban environments and interventions on mental health and wellbeing at the neighbourhood scale. The primary goal is to translate complex neuro-psycho-physiological and environmental data into easy-to understand and meaningful information for urban planners, policymakers, researchers, and communities.

At the core of the NUA outcomes is the **NUA-Index**. It is a combination of sub-indices related to selected categories of urban mental health in place. NUA index is a numeric score expressed in percentage value that summarizes assessment outcomes across urban mental health categories. Additionally, a traffic light system of graphical presentation facilitates the interpretation of results (see examples in Figure 13).

A.

B.

Figure 13. A. Examples of different NUA-indices represented with percentage values as well as the traffic-light system. B. NUA scale with colour coding referent to the traffic light system.

Five separate categories are combined under NUA index and are accessible when a more granular approach is required. These categories include:

Neurophysiology: objective data from mobile EEG (mEEG) and Heart Rate (HR), reflecting brain activity and autonomic nervous system responses related to states like stress, relaxation, alertness, and engagement. These refer to the self-administered recording sessions at the site and are averaged across all participants.

Wellbeing: Subjective data from questionnaires focused on mental health (stress, anxiety, depression).

Community Bonding: Measures related to the sense of community and sense of place within the neighbourhood.

Lifestyle: Self-reported screen time, sleep quality, playtime outdoors, substance use.

Environmental Quality Metrics: Objective spatial and environmental measures characterizing the built and natural environment, such as connectivity, canopy cover area, permeable surface ratio, presence of specific Nature-Based Solutions (NbS), noise levels, thermal comfort, air quality, and landscape visual quality (assessed via the Contemplative Landscape Model - CLM).

The NUA index provides an aggregated score that summarizes the overall mental wellbeing status of a neighbourhood, influenced by its environment. This index allows for a quick and intuitive grasp of the assessment's findings, enabling stakeholders to see the overall impact of the environment or intervention on mental health. **Appendix 4** presents the example of how the outputs could look like and what they contain. The following subsections elaborate on the interpretation and use of results, as well as the limitations and integrations of the outcomes with the other GreenInCities project outcomes.

4.1 NUA Integrations

In recent years, the application of neuroscience in urban planning has emerged as a tool for designing healthier and more inclusive cities. NUA provides a scientific framework

for evaluating mental health impacts of urban environments using portable neuroimaging tools, which can be effectively integrated with other participatory and mapping techniques. By integrating neuroscientific insights with participatory urban planning approaches and digital twins as dynamic, real-time virtual replicas of a city or neighbourhood, cities can identify cognitive and emotional responses to different urban settings, ensuring that new interventions promote mental wellbeing, stress reduction, and cognitive comfort.

4.1.1 Connection with digital twins and mapping tools

The integration of NUA with the digital twin (especially Mental Health digital Twin, MHDT, developed under WP4) and urban mapping, including participatory mapping, can positively contribute to the multifaceted nature and comprehensiveness of the co-creation process by providing quantifiable evidence-based data of how urban environments affect mental health. This integration generally can follow the three stages of the co-creation process (1) co-analysis, 2) co-design and implementation, 3) co-monitoring), where NUA data can inform decision-making Figure 14.

Figure 14. Potential integration of NUA within the stages of the co-creation process. During co-analysis, neuroscience data is collected through quantitative diagnostics and integrated with participatory mapping results. In the co-design phase, digital twins and

Co-analysis

At this stage, quantitative and qualitative assessments are conducted to map the current mental health landscape of urban areas and to understand its qualities and potential. The existing study (Kaur et al., 2024) demonstrates that neurourbanism can use

brain-scanning tools to predict and understand the influence of urban environments on behaviour, thus enabling the design of cities that prioritize cognitive and emotional wellbeing. For example, NUA can be used to measure neural and physiological responses to various urban settings, creating cognitive and emotional heatmaps that can be overlaid on GIS-based urban diagnostic tools. Participatory approaches, such as mental mapping workshops, allow local communities to identify stress-inducing and calming environments, complementing neurophysiological data with subjective insights. Emotional maps can be also constructed from the outcomes of participatory workshops (for example, from the analysis of the text comments) and compared with NUA data. These findings can then be integrated into digital twin models (such as MHDT), creating a mental wellbeing layer within the virtual city representation.

Co-design and implementation

In the co-design phase, NUA can be applied for the real-time testing of urban design interventions proposals before they are implemented: AR (Augmented Reality) and VR (Virtual Reality) tools could be applied to allow citizens to immerse themselves in proposed urban environments, while real-time neurofeedback is collected to assess stress reduction, relaxation, and overall cognitive engagement. This process ensures that urban interventions are optimized for mental wellbeing, supporting evidence-based decision-making in public space design. By integrating neuro-data into digital twins (MHDT), urban planners can simulate different urban layouts and evaluate their effects on cognitive and emotional wellbeing. Already existing practical case studies show the value of these tools. In one 2020 experiment (Hu & Roberts, 2020), researchers simulated a new light-rail line in a virtual city environment and measured participants' brainwaves (EEG) as they "experienced" the future infrastructure. They found measurable changes in emotional arousal when key urban design elements (like station layouts and green space) were varied, proving that VR-based digital city twins combined with EEG can predict how infrastructure changes might influence residents' stress and relaxation levels. This example illustrates how digital twins, GIS mapping, and immersive simulations are being used as neuro-urban laboratories allowing cities to be "felt" and assessed through the brain's responses in the design stage before real-world implementation. The approach is highly interdisciplinary, merging urban planning with neuroscience and data sciences.

Co-monitoring (and prediction)

Post-intervention analysis is essential to ensure that urban changes deliver long-term benefits for mental health. Through longitudinal neuro-data collection, continuous EEG monitoring applied together with participatory evaluation tools, the effectiveness of interventions can be tracked over time. Digital twins are updated with real-world NUA data, providing an adaptive urban mental health monitoring system. This integration would allow cities to refine their strategies, ensuring that mental wellbeing remains a central focus of sustainable urban development. Moreover AI-driven models (MHDT)

could be applied to predict the mental wellbeing impact of new green spaces by simulating pre- and post-intervention brain data. This would eliminate the need for constant human testing while forecasting how nature-based solutions will affect community stress or mood. As a result, planners can test urban design alternatives more easily and choose options that maximize positive neural and emotional outcomes (Egbosimba, 2025).

4.1.2 Relevant Initiatives – potential for NUA integrations.

Researchers are now combining neuroscience methods with urban data to inform planning. Population-scale studies funded by the EU are leveraging big data, brain imaging, and geospatial analytics. Some examples of the recent and ongoing European projects involving them are presented in **Annex 7**.

The integration of neuroscience-driven urban planning, participatory mapping, and digital twin technologies represents a step towards designing mentally healthier cities. By embedding NUA within the GreenInCities co-creation framework, urban interventions can be designed, tested, and validated based on real-world neurobiological data.

The NUA approach highlights how interdisciplinary collaboration can be further formalized in governance. Traditionally, urban planning with participatory and digital twinning practices and public health/mental health operated in separate silos. Neurourbanism assessment can bridge this gap.

4.2 Limitations and risks

NUA operates within certain constraints. However, many of these perceived limitations and risks are precisely where the NUA's innovative design offers valuable contributions and opportunities for deeper understanding and for action. Table 6 below presents the risks and mitigation measures to address them, as listed below.

One of the key considerations and potential source of biased results includes the representativeness of sampling in real-world settings. Traditional neuroscience studies often rely on easily accessible, but potentially unrepresentative "WEIRD" samples, limiting the generalizability of findings. NUA is designed to actively recruit participants from the target neighbourhood's resident population, ensuring that the data reflects the diverse experiences of the actual users of the space. This commitment to recruiting real-life residents is an opportunity and a challenge at the same time.

Another bottleneck is the risk of noisy physiological data. Collecting physiological data like EEG and HR in dynamic, real-world urban environments inevitably present challenges with noise and artifacts. NUA leverages recent technological advancements in mobile EEG devices, such as miniaturization, wireless transmission, longer battery life, dry electrodes, and active electrodes, specifically designed to improve signal quality

and ease of use in non-laboratory settings. Furthermore, the methodology incorporates rigorous preprocessing pipelines, including filtering and automatic artifact detection, to effectively manage noise and ensure the reliability of the objective data captured in-situ.

NUA's in-situ methodology means it is naturally sensitive to environmental conditions like weather. While this might make data collection in harsh conditions less feasible in certain climates, it also underscores NUA's strength in capturing realistic patterns of public space use. Recognizing this sensitivity allows for planning studies during appropriate times and highlights the importance of considering seasonal variations in urban design and their potential impact on wellbeing.

Furthermore, it is acknowledged that mental wellbeing is influenced by a myriad of factors beyond the immediate environment, such as significant personal life events or broader socioeconomic changes. A single NUA assessment provides only a snapshot; therefore, more timepoints or continuous monitoring is recommended to observe nuanced fluctuations in wellbeing and better understand how environmental impacts intersect with other ongoing factors. The inclusion of detailed self-report questionnaires covering lifestyle and socio-demographics provides crucial contextual data for analysis, acknowledging these important moderating factors

Finally, the integration of neuroscience-driven urban assessment is still quite novel, and urban planning processes and municipal budgets may not traditionally prioritize mental health metrics or allocate specific expenditure for such assessments. But the times are changing and tools for urban decision-makers to justify investments in projects that promote mental health, and integrate mental health considerations systematically into planning, might gain a higher place on the list of priorities.

The following Table 10 summarizes the key risks identified within the NUA methodology and their corresponding mitigation measures

Table 10. Risks and risk mitigation measures of NUA.

Risk Description	Likelihood	Impact	Mitigation Measures
Safety for researchers and equipment at the site.	Potentially high depending on the location	Injury, damage to equipment, inability to complete the assessment	Choose safe locations, take safety measures to protect researchers and equipment, such as adequate insurance policy.
Limited engagement of residents during recruitment.	Medium	Reduced diversity in participants, biased data, limited community ownership.	Employ diverse and multi-pronged recruitment strategies such as flyers, on-site recruitment, word of mouth, social media, workshops, community and gatekeeper engagement, local government support.

Exclusion of specific groups during recruitment due to language barriers or lack of comfort with technology.	Medium	Inequity in representation, potentially biased results	Use multiple recruitment methods and ensure communication in the participant's language.
Loss of connection with participants during the study.	Low	Reduced engagement, limited feedback, missing data.	Maintain ongoing engagement through regular communication, social media, and integration of participant feedback.
Ethical issues around data use and care.	Low	Loss of trust, participant harm, invalid data	Empower participants around their data use and care, speak the participants language.
Data integrity issues during export and preprocessing (e.g. loss of participant code, issues with file format, missing channel information, artifacts).	Medium to High	Inaccurate results, compromised data analysis	Implement data management protocols, verify data integrity, and use data visualization to detect artifacts.
Self-report data entries are random, extreme, or missing.	Medium	Skewed or inaccurate results.	Check for missing data and flag any extreme or random entries.
Participant disengagement or drop-out due to complicated recording setup with a high number of electrodes.	Medium	Incomplete or unreliable data.	Use a manageable number of electrodes and user-friendly equipment that are easy to set up.
Potential issues with the mEEG device impacting data quality and ease of use.	Low	Poor quality or unusable data	Carefully select EEG device based on criteria such as wireless, storage, battery, sampling rate, dry electrodes, active electrodes.

5. Planning and Management

5.1 Resources

This section outlines the essential resources required for the effective implementation of the Neurourbanism Assessment (NUA) methodology. These resources encompass the necessary personnel, the timing required for assessments, and the types of input data utilized to ensure the integrity and reliability of the NUA findings.

5.1.1 Personnel

For NUA execution, the primary personnel needed include a neuroscience expert to interpret the results. Additionally, a data collection manager/officer is required, who should be familiar with the methodology guidelines presented in this deliverable or have attended a specialized workshop on it.

During the execution phase, members of the NUA team or researchers are directly involved in:

- Conducting in-person recruitment.
- Guiding participants through technical setup and device placement.
- Monitoring participant compliance during data collection sessions.
- Checking the proper completion of self-report questionnaires.
- Providing ongoing support to participants during at-home recording.

Furthermore, trained data analysts are needed for the data analysis steps, including preprocessing and statistical analysis. To ensure ethical practices and data protection, a Principal Investigator is responsible for securely storing paper-based data, and an authorized data officer manages contact information. Local translators are also crucial when language barriers exist, ensuring participants fully understand the study information and consent process.

A distinguishing feature of NUA is its citizen science approach, which involves actively engaging community members or residents in data collection and feedback processes. Participants are empowered to collect their own neurophysiological data using easy-to-operate mobile EEG devices after receiving training. This approach fosters community ownership of mental health outcomes and enhances the ecological validity of the data.

5.1.2 Required timing

It is advisable to monitor mental health and wellbeing in relation to the living environment on a regular basis, such as once yearly, over a period of 6 months to 1 year. This continuous monitoring helps track the effects of ongoing social, demographic, and environmental changes on mental wellbeing.

A single NUA assessment is performed over seven days. This seven-day protocol includes:

- An enrolment day (lasting approximately one to one and a half hours) where participants give informed consent, register, receive training on device usage, and objective neurophysiological measures are captured during an initial on-site exploration
- Five subsequent days during which participants autonomously collect data using loaned devices, performing three recording sessions (one identical to the on-site session, and two at home during daily activities). They also complete daily short-term emotional state questionnaires
- A final day for participants to return the devices, complete complementary reports, and receive incentives.

The timing of recruitment is critical to the internal validity of the NUA methodology, as urban lifestyle and mental wellbeing are sensitive to seasonal variation. Therefore, data collection and recruitment should ideally unfold within a single season to avoid confounding influences from changes in daylight, temperature, or vegetation. Recruitment should be launched at the beginning of a season, with the data collection period taking place at the end, providing at least one to two months of lead time for awareness-raising and participant pipeline building.

5.1.3 Input data

The input data for NUA is multi-modal and comprehensive, integrating various types of measures to ensure a robust assessment. This includes:

- **Local population data:** This is crucial for participant recruitment and is typically gathered through online forms. It helps ensure the recruitment of a diverse and representative cross-section of each neighborhood, enhancing the relevance of findings for local communities. Participants are recruited from the target area's resident population to ensure representativeness. Eligibility criteria include being healthy adults (18+), without a neurological or psychiatric diagnosis, and being right-handed. The target sample size is a minimum of 50 individuals per urban neighborhood.
- **"Data privacy agreement" policies:** These must be established between the data collector and participants. NUA adheres strictly to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and bioethics standards, ensuring responsible data collection and implementation. Key ethical procedures include the informed consent process where participants receive comprehensive information about the study's purpose, procedures, minimal risks, and data management. Participants are assured of confidentiality for their responses and data and have the right to withdraw from the study at any point without

penalty. Personal information is separated from research data, with only a unique, random participant code used for data handling.

5.1.4 Software and Hardware Selection

NUA relies on specialised software and carefully selected portable EEG devices to ensure accurate, efficient, and user-friendly data collection in real-world urban environments. The software must support key functions such as signal cleaning, frequency analysis, and statistical modelling, while also being accessible to research teams with varying technical backgrounds. Similarly, mobile EEG devices must balance signal quality with comfort, ease of use, and compatibility with outdoor data collection. As part of this deliverable, a detailed comparison of software options and device specifications is provided in **Annex 7**.

5.2 Data management

This section outlines the procedures for managing data collected during the Neurourbanism Assessment (NUA), ensuring data integrity, security, and compliance with ethical and legal standards. The data management plan covers the entire lifecycle of the data, from collection to storage, analysis, and eventual disposal.

As a principle, NUA gathers various data types, including physiological data (EEG and HR) from wearable devices, self-report data from questionnaires and surveys, and spatial and environmental data. A mobile application is used for data collection, which encrypts the data and transmits it to a designated database, without storing or processing it locally. Participants are assigned a unique, random code for anonymization.

5.2.1 Data Storage and Security

Personal information is separated from research data and only a unique, random participant code is used for all data handling, scheduling and storage.

- **Paper-based data** is stored securely in a locked cabinet, accessible only to the Principal Investigator.
- **Electronic data** is stored in encrypted form on password-protected computers.
- **Databases do not contain subject identifiers**, and the data linking subject identifiers and subject identification codes will be stored separately and discarded once data collection is completed.
- **Data from the mobile application are encrypted** and directly transmitted to a dedicated server.

- **Coded data is stored securely** for 10 years at the premises of the GreenInCities consortium partners, adhering to Intellectual Property regulations in the grant agreement and the Data Management Policy.
- Access to raw research data is **restricted to authorized researchers**. Contact information is only accessible to an authorized data officer

5.2.2 Data Processing and Analysis

NUA EEG data is pre-processed using validated neuroscience procedures, including:

- down sampling and re-referencing,
- segmentation into epochs,
- artifact detection and removal
- filtering for alpha and beta frequency bands.

Data Integrity is ensured by:

- Ensuring the participant code is maintained during data transfer
- Converting data to a portable format like EDF
- Verifying the header information
- Visually monitoring data for artifacts
- Checking for event markers

Self-report data is prepared by:

- Transferring paper data to an electronic format.
- Checking for personal identifiers, missing data, random or extreme entries.
- Scoring standardized instruments according to their guidelines

Data analysis is performed using statistical modelling, more specifically: EEG data analysis includes computation of average absolute power for each electrode and a baseline. Self-report data will be analyzed using t-tests.

5.2.3 Data Sharing, Re-use and Integration

Data is managed according to the GreenInCities project's data management policy. All data can be re-used for future research in line with ethical guidelines.

5.2.4. Participant rights

Informed consent is obtained after providing full information about the research, procedures and data management practices. All participant responses and data are kept confidential. Participants have the right to withdraw from the study at any point. Moreover, participants can access, rectify, erase, or restrict processing of their data by providing their personal identifier. Participants are informed that no incidental findings will be shared with them.

6. Conclusion

The journey of developing the Neurourbanism Assessment (NUA) methodology, as detailed in this deliverable, represents an important advancement at the intersection of urban planning and mental health research. As a result of an interdisciplinary effort led by scientists from NeuroLandscape (see in Figure 15), and supported by IAAC, ABUD, KTU, and LAND within the GreenInCities consortium, NUA offers a comprehensive, robust, and accessible framework for evaluating the impacts of urban environments on human wellbeing at the neighbourhood scale.

Figure 15. Team of Researchers from NeuroLandscape (from left: Dr. Nicolas Escoffier, Dr. Agnieszka Olszewska-Guizzo and Anastasia Kokkinou), developers of NUA and authors of this deliverable, at the first day of NUA data collection in the marginalized community in Nova Gorica, Slovenia, April 2025.

NUA shifts the focus from diagnosing individuals with mental health issues to a "diagnosis of the space," providing valuable insights into how the human brain responds to its surroundings. This novel approach can inform a diverse range of stakeholders, including urban planners, policymakers, researchers, and, most critically, residents themselves. By combining established global psychometrics (such as WHO Quality of Life or Perceived Stress Scale among others), with neuroscience-informed measures, NUA ensures a comprehensive and reliable assessment. Its primary output, the NUA-Index, provides an easy-to-understand numeric score, allowing for rapid and actionable interpretation of complex findings. Importantly, NUA is firmly grounded in bioethics, upholding the highest standards of data privacy, anonymity and participant safety throughout the entire assessment process. The NUA protocol, encompassing enrolment, autonomous data collection, and follow-up, has been designed for practical application, enabling longitudinal pre- and post-intervention assessments to quantify tangible improvements in wellbeing. The seamless integration of NUA with digital twins and urban mapping tools will further extend its utility, enabling co-analysis, co-design, and continuous co-monitoring of urban interventions.

References

- Abdel-Ghany, A., Al-Helal, I., & Shady, M. (2013). Human thermal comfort and heat stress in an outdoor urban arid environment: a case study. *Advances in Meteorology*, 2013(1), 693541.
- Abrahamse, W. (2019). Chapter 1 - Introduction. In W. Abrahamse (Ed.), *Encouraging Pro-Environmental Behaviour* (pp. 3-10). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-811359-2.00001-9>
- Adli, M., Berger, M., Brakemeier, E.-L., Engel, L., Fingerhut, J., Gomez-Carrillo, A., Hehl, R., Heinz, A., H, J. M., Mehran, N., Tolaas, S., Walter, H., Weiland, U., & Stollmann, J. (2017). Neurourbanism: towards a new discipline. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 4(3), 183-185. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(16\)30371-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(16)30371-6)
- Assembly, U. G. (2006). Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. *Ga Res*, 61, 106.
- Astell-Burt, T., & Feng, X. (2019). Association of urban green space with mental health and general health among adults in Australia. *JAMA network open*, 2(7), e198209-e198209.
- Attaianese, E., & Barilà, M. (2023). Inclusive mental well-being through environmental design. *E3S Web of Conferences*,
- Baevsky, R. M., & Chernikova, A. G. (2017). Heart rate variability analysis: physiological foundations and main methods. *Cardiometry*(10).
- Bakker, M., & Wicherts, J. M. (2014). Outlier removal and the relation with reporting errors and quality of psychological research. *PloS one*, 9(7), e103360.
- Banerjee, T., & Baer, W. C. (2013). *Beyond the neighborhood unit: Residential environments and public policy*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Beauchamp, T. L., & Childress, J. F. (1994). *Principles of biomedical ethics*. Edicoes Loyola.
- Beck, D., & Mitkiewicz, J. (2025). A systematic literature review of citizen science in urban studies and regional urban planning: policy, practical, and research implications. *Urban Ecosystems*, 28(2), 1-21.
- Berman, M. G., Jonides, J., & Kaplan, S. (2008). The cognitive benefits of interacting with nature. *Psychol Sci*, 19(12), 1207-1212. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9280.2008.02225.x>
- Bernard, J. Y., Padmapriya, N., Chen, B., Cai, S., Tan, K. H., Yap, F., Shek, L., Chong, Y. S., Gluckman, P. D., Godfrey, K. M., Kramer, M. S., Saw, S. M., & Müller-Riemenschneider, F. (2017). Predictors of screen viewing time in young Singaporean children: the GUSTO cohort. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act*, 14(1), 112. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-017-0562-3>
- Berntson, G. G., Thomas Bigger Jr, J., Eckberg, D. L., Grossman, P., Kaufmann, P. G., Malik, M., Nagaraja, H. N., Porges, S. W., Saul, J. P., & Stone, P. H. (1997). Heart rate variability: origins, methods, and interpretive caveats. *Psychophysiology*, 34(6), 623-648.
- Beute, F., Davies, Z. G., de Vries, S., Glanville, J., Keune, H., Lammel, A., Marselle, M., O'Brien, L., Olszewska-Guizzo, A., & Remmen, R. (2020). Types and characteristics of urban and peri-urban blue spaces having an impact on human mental health and wellbeing: a systematic review.

- Beute, F., Marselle, M. R., Olszewska-Guizzo, A., Andreucci, M., Lammel, A., Davies, Z. G., Glanville, J., Keune, H., O'Brien, L., & Remmen, R. (2023). How do different types and characteristics of green space impact mental health? A scoping review. *People and Nature*, 5(6), 1839-1876.
- Beveridge, C., & Hoffman, C. (1997). *The papers of Frederick Law Olmsted* (Vol. 1). Johns Hopkins Press.
- Bjørndal, L. D., Ebrahimi, O. V., Lan, X., Nes, R. B., & Røysamb, E. (2024). Mental health and environmental factors in adults: A population-based network analysis. *American Psychologist*, 79(3), 368.
- Bonaccorsi, G., Milani, C., Giorgetti, D., Setola, N., Naldi, E., Manzi, F., Del Riccio, M., Dellisanti, C., & Lorini, C. (2023). Impact of Built Environment and Neighborhood on Promoting Mental Health, Well-being, and Social Participation in Older People: an Umbrella Review. *Annali di Igiene, Medicina Preventiva e di Comunità*, 35(2).
- Bonifácio, A., Morgado, P., Peponi, A., Ancora, L., Mora, D. A. B., Conceição, M., & Miranda, B. (2023). Musings on neurourbanism, public space and urban health. *Finisterra: Revista Portuguesa de Geografia*, 58(122), 63-88.
- Bonney, R., Phillips, T. B., Ballard, H. L., & Enck, J. W. (2016). Can citizen science enhance public understanding of science? *Public understanding of science*, 25(1), 2-16.
- Bonney, R., Shirk, J. L., Phillips, T. B., Wiggins, A., Ballard, H. L., Miller-Rushing, A. J., & Parrish, J. K. (2014). Next steps for citizen science. *Science*, 343(6178), 1436-1437.
- Bratman, G. N., Anderson, C. B., Berman, M. G., Cochran, B., de Vries, S., Flanders, J., Folke, C., Frumkin, H., Gross, J. J., Hartig, T., Kahn, P. H., Kuo, M., Lawler, J. J., Levin, P. S., Lindahl, T., Meyer-Lindenberg, A., Mitchell, R., Ouyang, Z., Roe, J., Scarlett, L., Smith, J. R., van den Bosch, M., Wheeler, B. W., White, M. P., Zheng, H., & Daily, G. C. (2019). Nature and mental health: An ecosystem service perspective. *Science Advances*, 5(7), eaax0903. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aax0903>
- Bratman, G. N., Hamilton, J. P., & Daily, G. C. (2012). The impacts of nature experience on human cognitive function and mental health. *Annals of the New York academy of sciences*, 1249(1), 118-136.
- Brewer, M. B., & Crano, W. D. (2000). Research design and issues of validity. *Handbook of research methods in social and personality psychology*, 3-16.
- Bronfenbrenner, U. (1977). Toward an experimental ecology of human development. *American Psychologist*, 32(7), 513.
- Brunswik, E. (1955). Representative design and probabilistic theory in a functional psychology. *Psychological review*, 62(3), 193.
- Callan, D. E., Torre-Tresols, J. J., Laguerta, J., & Ishii, S. (2024). Shredding artifacts: extracting brain activity in EEG from extreme artifacts during skateboarding using ASR and ICA. *Frontiers in neuroergonomics*, 5, 1358660.
- Castells, M. (1999). Grassrooting the space of flows. *Urban geography*, 20(4), 294-302.
- Catherine Horwill, & Elli Thomas. (2019). Inclusive Design: Beyond Accessibility. *World Architecture Magazine China*.
- Cohen, M. X. (2014). *Analyzing neural time series data: theory and practice*. MIT press.
- Cohen, S., Kamarck, T., & Mermelstein, R. (1983). A global measure of perceived stress. *Journal of health and social behavior*, 385-396.
- Commission, E., Research, D.-G. f., & Innovation. (2020). *Citizen Science – Elevating research and innovation through societal engagement*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/doi/10.2777/624713>

- Cooley, C. H. (2001). Extrait de Social Organization. A Study of the Larger Mind. *HERMÈS*, 31, 55.
- Cooley, J. W., & Tukey, J. W. (1965). An algorithm for the machine calculation of complex Fourier series. *Mathematics of computation*, 19(90), 297-301.
- Cumming, G., Fidler, F., Kalinowski, P., & Lai, J. (2012). The statistical recommendations of the American Psychological Association Publication Manual: Effect sizes, confidence intervals, and meta-analysis. *Australian Journal of Psychology*, 64(3), 138-146.
- Cummings, J. J., & Bailenson, J. N. (2016). How immersive is enough? A meta-analysis of the effect of immersive technology on user presence. *Media psychology*, 19(2), 272-309.
- Davidson, R. J. (2004). What does the prefrontal cortex "do" in affect: perspectives on frontal EEG asymmetry research. *Biological psychology*, 67(1-2), 219-234.
- Delorme, A., & Martin, J. A. (2021). Automated data cleaning for the Muse EEG. 2021 IEEE International Conference on Bioinformatics and Biomedicine (BIBM),
- Dolan, R. J. (2002). Emotion, cognition, and behavior. *Science*, 298(5596), 1191-1194.
- EC. (2021). *New European Bauhaus – Commission Communication* (COM2021 573 final, Issue).
- Egan, M., Katikireddi, S. V., Kearns, A., Tannahill, C., Kalacs, M., & Bond, L. (2013). Health effects of neighborhood demolition and housing improvement: a prospective controlled study of 2 natural experiments in urban renewal. *American Journal of Public Health*, 103(6), e47-e53.
- Egbosimba, B. (2025). Urbanization and Mental Health: Rethinking Public Spaces to Support Well-being. *International Journal of Healthcare Sciences*, 12(2), 71-83. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14788866>
- Engel, A. K., & Fries, P. (2010). Beta-band oscillations—signalling the status quo? *Current opinion in neurobiology*, 20(2), 156-165.
- Engemann, K., Pedersen, C. B., Arge, L., Tsirogiannis, C., Mortensen, P. B., & Svenning, J.-C. (2019). Residential green space in childhood is associated with lower risk of psychiatric disorders from adolescence into adulthood. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 116(11), 5188. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1807504116>
- Forster, G. K., Aarø, L. E., Alme, M. N., Hansen, T., Nilsen, T. S., & Vedaa, Ø. (2023). Built environment accessibility and disability as predictors of well-being among older adults: A Norwegian cross-sectional study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(10), 5898.
- Freeman, L. (2001). The effects of sprawl on neighborhood social ties: An explanatory analysis. *Journal of the American planning association*, 67(1), 69-77.
- Frumkin, H., Bratman, G. N., Breslow, S. J., Cochran, B., Kahn Jr, P. H., Lawler, J. J., Levin, P. S., Tandon, P. S., Varanasi, U., & Wolf, K. L. (2017). Nature contact and human health: A research agenda. *Environmental health perspectives*, 125(7), 075001.
- Gehl, J. (2013). *Cities for people*. Island press.
- Gillerot, L., Rozario, K., De Frenne, P., Oh, R., Ponette, Q., Bonn, A., Chow, W., Godbold, D., Steinparzer, M., & Haluza, D. (2024). Forests are chill: The interplay between thermal comfort and mental wellbeing. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 242, 104933.
- Gramann, K. (2024). Mobile EEG for neurourbanism research-What could possibly go wrong? A critical review with guidelines. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 102308.

- Grande, G., Ljungman, P. L., Eneroth, K., Bellander, T., & Rizzuto, D. (2020). Association between cardiovascular disease and long-term exposure to air pollution with the risk of dementia. *JAMA neurology*, 77(7), 801-809.
- Heidegger, M. (1951). Building dwelling thinking. *Visual culture: Critical concepts in media and cultural studies*, 3, 66-76.
- Heiskanen, T. (2012). Spaces, places and communities of practice. In *Information society and the workplace* (pp. 3-25). Routledge.
- Howcutt, S. J., Barnett, A. L., Barbosa-Boucas, S., & Smith, L. A. (2018). Research recruitment: A marketing framework to improve sample representativeness in health research. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 74(4), 968-975.
- Hsu, S.-H., Pion-Tonachini, L., Palmer, J., Miyakoshi, M., Makeig, S., & Jung, T.-P. (2018). Modeling brain dynamic state changes with adaptive mixture independent component analysis. *Neuroimage*, 183, 47-61.
- Hu, M., & Roberts, J. (2020). Built environment evaluation in virtual reality environments—a cognitive neuroscience approach. *Urban science*, 4(4), 48.
- Humphreys, D. K., Panter, J., Sahlqvist, S., Goodman, A., & Ogilvie, D. (2016). Changing the environment to improve population health: a framework for considering exposure in natural experimental studies. *J Epidemiol Community Health*, 70(9), 941-946.
- Hunkin, H., King, D. L., & Zajac, I. T. (2021). Evaluating the feasibility of a consumer-grade wearable EEG headband to aid assessment of state and trait mindfulness. *Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 77(11), 2559-2575.
- Ingold, T. (1993). The temporality of the landscape. *World archaeology*, 25(2), 152-174.
- Iriarte, J., Urrestarazu, E., Valencia, M., Alegre, M., Malanda, A., Viteri, C., & Artieda, J. (2003). Independent component analysis as a tool to eliminate artifacts in EEG: a quantitative study. *Journal of clinical neurophysiology*, 20(4), 249-257.
- Irwin, A. (2002). *Citizen science: A study of people, expertise and sustainable development*. Routledge.
- Jacobs, A., & Appleyard, D. (1987). Toward an urban design manifesto. *Journal of the American planning association*, 53(1), 112-120.
- [Record #791 is using a reference type undefined in this output style.]
- Jasper, H. H. (1958). Ten-twenty electrode system of the international federation. *Electroencephalogr Clin Neurophysiol*, 10, 371-375.
- Jesulola, E., Sharpley, C. F., Bitsika, V., Agnew, L. L., & Wilson, P. (2015). Frontal alpha asymmetry as a pathway to behavioural withdrawal in depression: Research findings and issues. *Behavioural brain research*, 292, 56-67.
- Juengst, S. B., Kumar, R. G., Holland, A., Cohen, A., Nelson, T. A., Corrigan, J. D., Sander, A. M., Perrin, P. B., Venkatesan, U. M., & Rabinowitz, A. (2025). Effects of Home Neighborhood Tree Canopy Coverage on Mental Health Outcomes: A Traumatic Brain Injury Model Systems Investigation. *The Journal of Head Trauma Rehabilitation*, 10.1097.
- Kaur, A., Rodrigues, A. L., Hoogstraten, S., Blanco-Mora, D. A., Miranda, B., Morgado, P., & Meshi, D. (2024). Functional brain imaging predicts population-level visits to urban spaces. *bioRxiv*, 2024.2002. 2016.580650.
- Kim, J., & Kaplan, R. (2004). Physical and psychological factors in sense of community: New urbanist Kentlands and nearby Orchard Village. *Environment and Behavior*, 36(3), 313-340.
- Klement, J., Rienow, A., Daniel, C., & Terlau, W. (2025). Inclusive urban planning: leveraging citizen science for community well-being. *Cities & Health*, 1-12.

- Kroenke, K., Strine, T. W., Spitzer, R. L., Williams, J. B., Berry, J. T., & Mokdad, A. H. (2009). The PHQ-8 as a measure of current depression in the general population. *Journal of affective disorders, 114*(1-3), 163-173.
- Lämås, K., Bölenius, K., Sandman, P. O., Bergland, Å., Lindkvist, M., & Edvardsson, D. (2020). Thriving among older people living at home with home care services—A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Advanced Nursing, 76*(4), 999-1008.
- Lederbogen, F., Kirsch, P., Haddad, L., Streit, F., Tost, H., Schuch, P., Wüst, S., Pruessner, J. C., Rietschel, M., & Deuschle, M. (2011). City living and urban upbringing affect neural social stress processing in humans. *Nature, 474*(7352), 498-501.
- Lefebvre, H., & Nicholson-Smith, D. (1991). *The production of space* (Vol. 142). Oxford Blackwell.
- Li, G., Sun, G. X., Ren, Y., Luo, X. S., & Zhu, Y. G. (2018). Urban soil and human health: a review. *European Journal of Soil Science, 69*(1), 196-215.
- Lidwell, W., Holden, K., & Butler, J. (2010). *Universal principles of design, revised and updated: 125 ways to enhance usability, influence perception, increase appeal, make better design decisions, and teach through design*. Rockport Pub.
- Lovell, R., Husk, K., Cooper, C., Stahl-Timmins, W., & Garside, R. (2015). Understanding how environmental enhancement and conservation activities may benefit health and wellbeing: a systematic review. *BMC Public Health, 15*, 1-18.
- Lu, J. G. (2020). Air pollution: A systematic review of its psychological, economic, and social effects. *Current opinion in psychology, 32*, 52-65.
- Luck, S. J. (2014). *An introduction to the event-related potential technique*. MIT press.
- Manning, N. (2019). Sociology, biology and mechanisms in urban mental health. *Social Theory & Health, 17*, 1-22.
- McDougle, L. M., Greenspan, I., & Handy, F. (2011). Generation green: Understanding the motivations and mechanisms influencing young adults' environmental volunteering. *International Journal of Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Marketing, 16*(4), 325-341.
- McEwen, B. S., & Gianaros, P. J. (2010). Central role of the brain in stress and adaptation: links to socioeconomic status, health, and disease. *Annals of the New York academy of sciences, 1186*(1), 190-222.
- Meidenbauer, K. L., Schertz, K. E., Li, P., Sharma, A., Freeman, T. R., Janey, E. A., Stier, A. J., Samtani, A. L., Gehrke, K., & Berman, M. G. (2024). Variable and dynamic associations between hot weather, thermal comfort, and individuals' emotional states during summertime. *BMC psychology, 12*(1), 504.
- Melanie Davern, Verity Cleland, Kim Jose, Yvonne Laird, Samantha Rowbotham, Anna Timperio, Lynden Leppard, Kate Garvey, & Koirala, S. (2022). *Using citizen science to bring people back into planning walkable and healthy places*. Retrieved 8 May from <https://thefifthstate.com.au/columns/spinifex/using-citizen-science-to-bring-people-back-into-planning-walkable-and-healthy-places/>
- Micheline, G., Salmastyan, G., Vera, J. D., & Lenartowicz, A. (2022). Event-related brain oscillations in attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD): A systematic review and meta-analysis. *International journal of psychophysiology, 174*, 29-42.
- [Record #679 is using a reference type undefined in this output style.]
- Mindell, J. S., & Watkins, S. J. (2024). Transport, health and inequality. An overview of current evidence. *Journal of Transport & Health, 38*, 101886. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jth.2024.101886>

- Mucci, N., Traversini, V., Lorini, C., De Sio, S., Galea, R. P., Bonaccorsi, G., & Arcangeli, G. (2020). Urban noise and psychological distress: A systematic review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(18), 6621.
- Mullen, T. R., Kothe, C. A., Chi, Y. M., Ojeda, A., Kerth, T., Makeig, S., Jung, T.-P., & Cauwenberghs, G. (2015). Real-time neuroimaging and cognitive monitoring using wearable dry EEG. *IEEE transactions on biomedical engineering*, 62(11), 2553-2567.
- Murray, G., Judd, F., Jackson, H., Fraser, C., Komiti, A., Hodgins, G., Pattison, P., Humphreys, J., & Robins, G. (2004). Rurality and mental health: the role of accessibility. *Australian & New Zealand Journal of Psychiatry*, 38(8), 629-634.
- Nunez, P. L., & Srinivasan, R. (2006). *Electric fields of the brain: the neurophysics of EEG*. Oxford university press.
- Nutsford, D., Pearson, A. L., & Kingham, S. (2013). An ecological study investigating the association between access to urban green space and mental health. *Public health*, 127(11), 1005-1011.
- Nyquist, H. (2009). Certain topics in telegraph transmission theory. *Transactions of the American Institute of Electrical Engineers*, 47(2), 617-644.
- Okkels, N., Kristiansen, C. B., Munk-Jørgensen, P., & Sartorius, N. (2018). Urban mental health: challenges and perspectives. *Current Opinion in Psychiatry*, 31(3), 258-264. <https://doi.org/10.1097/yco.0000000000000413>
- Olszewska-Guizzo, A. (2023). *Neuroscience for Designing Green Spaces: Contemplative Landscapes*. Taylor & Francis.
- Olszewska-Guizzo, A., Escoffier, N., Chan, J., & Puay Yok, T. (2018). Window View and the Brain: Effects of Floor Level and Green Cover on the Alpha and Beta Rhythms in a Passive Exposure EEG Experiment. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*, 15(11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15112358>
- Olszewska-Guizzo, A., Escoffier, N., & Sia, A. (2022). Revised Contemplative Landscape Model (CLM-II): A Reliable and Valid Evaluation Tool for Mental Health-Promoting Urban Green Spaces. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, in peer-review.
- Olszewska-Guizzo, A., Fogel, A., Benjumea, D., & Tahsin, N. (2022). Sustainable Solutions in Urban Health: Transdisciplinary Directions in Urban Planning for Global Public Health. In *Sustainable Policies and Practices in Energy, Environment and Health Research* (pp. 223-243). Springer.
- Olszewska-Guizzo, A., Fogel, A., Escoffier, N., Sia, A., Nakazawa, K., Kumagai, A., Dan, I., & Ho, R. (2022). Therapeutic Garden With Contemplative Features Induces Desirable Changes in Mood and Brain Activity in Depressed Adults [Original Research]. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyt.2022.757056>
- Olszewska-Guizzo, A., Paiva, T. O., & Barbosa, F. (2018). Effects of 3D Contemplative Landscape Videos on Brain Activity in a Passive Exposure EEG Experiment. *Front Psychiatry*, 9, 317. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyt.2018.00317>
- Olszewska-Guizzo, A., Sia, A., & Escoffier, N. (2023). Revised Contemplative Landscape Model (CLM): A reliable and valid evaluation tool for mental health-promoting urban green spaces. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 86, 128016. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2023.128016>
- Olszewska-Guizzo, A., Sia, A., Fogel, A., & Ho, R. (2022). Features of Urban Green Spaces Associated with Positive Emotions, Mindfulness and Relaxation. *Scientific Reports*, (in press).

- Osborne, J. W., & Overbay, A. (2004). The power of outliers (and why researchers should always check for them). *Practical Assessment, Research, and Evaluation*, 9(1).
- Pallot, J., & Shaw, D. J. (2021). *Planning in the Soviet Union*. Routledge.
- Papadatou-Pastou, M., Ntolka, E., Schmitz, J., Martin, M., Munafò, M. R., Ocklenburg, S., & Paracchini, S. (2020). Human handedness: A meta-analysis. *Psychological bulletin*, 146(6), 481.
- Patricios, N. N. (2002). The neighborhood concept: a retrospective of physical design and social interaction. *Journal of Architectural and Planning Research*, 70-90.
- Peen, J., Schoevers, R. A., Beekman, A. T., & Dekker, J. (2010). The current status of urban-rural differences in psychiatric disorders. *Acta Psychiatr Scand*, 121(2), 84-93. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0447.2009.01438.x>
- Perry, C. A. (2004). *Early Urban Planning* (Vol. 7). Taylor & Francis.
- Peterson, N. A., Speer, P. W., & McMillan, D. W. (2008). Validation of a brief sense of community scale: Confirmation of the principal theory of sense of community. *Journal of community psychology*, 36(1), 61-73.
- Pitesa, M., & Gelfand, M. J. (2023). Going beyond Western, Educated, Industrialized, Rich, and Democratic (WEIRD) samples and problems in organizational research. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 174, 104212.
- Radüntz, T., Scouten, J., Hochmuth, O., & Meffert, B. (2017). Automated EEG artifact elimination by applying machine learning algorithms to ICA-based features. *Journal of neural engineering*, 14(4), 046004.
- Ramadier, T. (2004). Transdisciplinarity and its challenges: the case of urban studies. *Futures*, 36(4), 423-439.
- Rantakokko, M., Iwarsson, S., Portegijs, E., Viljanen, A., & Rantanen, T. (2015). Associations between environmental characteristics and life-space mobility in community-dwelling older people. *Journal of aging and health*, 27(4), 606-621.
- Rigolon, A., Browning, M. H., McAnirlin, O., & Yoon, H. (2021). Green space and health equity: a systematic review on the potential of green space to reduce health disparities. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(5), 2563.
- Robinson, L. D., Cawthray, J. L., West, S. E., Bonn, A., & Ansine, J. (2018). Ten principles of citizen science. In *Citizen science: Innovation in open science, society and policy* (pp. 27-40). UCL Press.
- Roe, J., & McCay, L. (2021). *Restorative Cities: Urban design for mental health and wellbeing*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- [Record #800 is using a reference type undefined in this output style.]
- Segrave, R. A., Cooper, N. R., Thomson, R., Croft, R. J., Sheppard, D., & Fitzgerald, P. (2011). Individualized alpha activity and frontal asymmetry in major depression. *Clinical EEG and neuroscience*, 42(1), 45-52.
- Shamay-Tsoory, S. G., & Mendelsohn, A. (2019). Real-life neuroscience: an ecological approach to brain and behavior research. *Perspectives on psychological science*, 14(5), 841-859.
- Shiffman, S., Stone, A. A., & Hufford, M. R. (2008). Ecological momentary assessment. *Annu. Rev. Clin. Psychol.*, 4(1), 1-32.
- Silver, C. (1985). Neighborhood planning in historical perspective. *Journal of the American planning association*, 51(2), 161-174.
- Smithson, M. (2003). *Confidence intervals*. Sage.

- Snodgrass, A., & Coyne, R. (2013). *Interpretation in architecture: design as way of thinking*. Routledge.
- Spitzer, R. L., Kroenke, K., Williams, J. B., & Löwe, B. (2006). A brief measure for assessing generalized anxiety disorder: the GAD-7. *Archives of internal medicine*, 166(10), 1092-1097.
- Ståhle, A. (2013). Sociotope mapping—exploring public open space and its multiple use values in urban and landscape planning practice. *NA*, 19(4).
- Stathopoulou, M. I., Cartalis, C., Keramitsoglou, I., & Santamouris, M. (2005). Thermal remote sensing of Thom's discomfort index (DI): Comparison with in-situ measurements. *Remote Sensing for Environmental Monitoring, GIS Applications, and Geology V*,
- Stroup, W. W., Ptukhina, M., & Garai, J. (2024). *Generalized linear mixed models: modern concepts, methods and applications*. Chapman and Hall/CRC.
- Thayer, J. F., Åhs, F., Fredrikson, M., Sollers III, J. J., & Wager, T. D. (2012). A meta-analysis of heart rate variability and neuroimaging studies: implications for heart rate variability as a marker of stress and health. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 36(2), 747-756.
- Todowede, O., Lewandowski, F., Kotera, Y., Ashmore, A., Rennick-Egglestone, S., Boyd, D., Moran, S., Ørjasæter, K. B., Repper, J., & Robotham, D. (2023). Best practice guidelines for citizen science in mental health research: systematic review and evidence synthesis. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 14, 1175311.
- Tost, H., Champagne, F. A., & Meyer-Lindenberg, A. (2015). Environmental influence in the brain, human welfare and mental health. *Nat Neurosci*, 18(10), 1421-1431. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn.4108>
- Tuan, Y.-F. (1997). Sense of place: what does it mean to be human? *American journal of theology & philosophy*, 47-58.
- Tuan, Y.-F. (2011). Topophilia and place experience. *Anekumene*(1), 8-13.
- Unell, J., & Castle, R. (2012). Developing sustainable volunteering within the Natural Connections Demonstration Project: A review of evidence. *Natural England Commissioned Report NECR096, (July)*, 36.
- van der Wal, J. M., van Borkulo, C. D., Deserno, M. K., Breedvelt, J. J., Lees, M., Lokman, J. C., Borsboom, D., Denys, D., van Holst, R. J., & Smidt, M. P. (2021). Advancing urban mental health research: from complexity science to actionable targets for intervention. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 8(11), 991-1000.
- Verbeek, T. (2014). Reconnecting urban planning and public health: an exploration of a more adaptive approach.
- Wagner, G. S., & Strauss, D. G. (2014). *Marriott's practical electrocardiography*. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- Wang, B., Ogburn, E. L., & Rosenblum, M. (2019). Analysis of covariance in randomized trials: More precision and valid confidence intervals, without model assumptions. *Biometrics*, 75(4), 1391-1400.
- West, S. E., & Pateman, R. M. (2016). Recruiting and retaining participants in citizen science: What can be learned from the volunteering literature? *Citizen science: Theory and practice*.
- Whitehead, M., & Dahlgren, G. (1991). What can be done about inequalities in health? *The Lancet*, 338(8774), 1059-1063.
- WHOqolGroup. (1998). Development of the World Health Organization WHOQOL-BREF quality of life assessment. *Psychological medicine*, 28(3), 551-558.

-
- Wood, L., Hooper, P., Foster, S., & Bull, F. (2017). Public green spaces and positive mental health—investigating the relationship between access, quantity and types of parks and mental wellbeing. *Health & place*, *48*, 63-71.
- Yemeru,, E., Arimah,, B., Otieno,, R. O., Oostrum,, M. v., Mutinda,, M., & Oginga-Martins, J. (2024). *Cities and Climate Action - World Cities report (World Cities Report 2024, Issue. U. N. H. S. P. (UN-Habitat). <https://unhabitat.org/wcr/>*
- Zhang, C., Wang, C., Chen, C., Tao, L., Jin, J., Wang, Z., & Jia, B. (2022). Effects of tree canopy on psychological distress: A repeated cross-sectional study before and during the COVID-19 epidemic. *Environmental Research*, *203*, 111795.

Annexes

Annex 1 – NUA Enrolment Questionnaire

Participant Code/ID:

Instructions:

Please circle or tick (✓) to provide an answer to all questions below. If you are unsure about which response to give to a question, please choose the one that appears most appropriate. This can often be your first response.

NP1	Residence type	a. Apartment in a multi-story building (owned or rented) b. Detached or semi-detached house (owned or rented) c. Social/municipal housing (government-subsidized rental flat or house) d. Other, please specify.....				
NP2	Room number	a. Studio b. 1-bedroom c. 2-bedroom d. 3-bedroom e. 4-bedroom & more				
NP3	People in the household	a. I live alone b. 2 people c. 3 people d. 4 people e. 5 people and more				
NP4	I've been living here for a long time.	Strongly Agree <input type="checkbox"/> 1	Somewhat Agree <input type="checkbox"/> 2	Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> 3	Somewhat Disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 4	Strongly Disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP5	Most of my family is from here.	Strongly Agree <input type="checkbox"/> 1	Somewhat Agree <input type="checkbox"/> 2	Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> 3	Somewhat Disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 4	Strongly Disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP6	Do you own any pets?	a. No b. Yes, please specify				
NP7	How often have you been spending <i>time alone</i> in Koren area at Panovec in the past month?	Never <input type="checkbox"/> 1	1-2 times <input type="checkbox"/> 2	3-5 times <input type="checkbox"/> 3	6-10 times <input type="checkbox"/> 4	More than 10 times <input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP8	How often have you been spending <i>time with others</i> in Koren area at Panovec in the past month?	Never <input type="checkbox"/> 1	1-2 times <input type="checkbox"/> 2	3-5 times <input type="checkbox"/> 3	6-10 times <input type="checkbox"/> 4	More than 10 times <input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP9	Do you have access to greenspace where you live?	a. Yes, shared green space (e.g. park) b. Yes, private green space (e.g. private garden) c. Yes, both shared and private green space d. Just a visual access (e.g. view from your home window) e. No access. f. Other.....				

NP10	<p>To what extent do you feel you have enough opportunities to access and engage with nature in your local area?</p> <p><i>By nature, we mean all types of natural environment and all the plants and animals living in them. Nature can be close to where you live in towns, the countryside, or wilderness areas further away</i></p>				
	Not at all	A little	A moderate amount	Very much	Extremely
	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP11	<p>How do you describe your neighbourhood in terms of wealth</p>		<p>a. Very poor b. Poor c. Average d. Wealthy e. Very wealthy</p>		

Please indicate the extent to which each of the following items have stopped you from engaging in nature in the last two weeks.

	Not at all	A little	A moderate amount	Very much	Extremely
NP12	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP13	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP14	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP15	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP16	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP17	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP18	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP19	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP20	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP21	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP22	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP23	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP24	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP25	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP26	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP27	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

NP28	Fear of animals/insects/plants	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP29	No particular reason	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP30	Don't know	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
NP31	Prefer not to say	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

Below are a set of statements about your neighbourhood. Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with these statements by placing a check mark in the appropriate box.

		Strongly Agree	Somewhat Agree	Neutral	Somewhat Disagree	Strongly Disagree
BC1	I can get what I need in this neighborhood.	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
BC2	This neighborhood helps me fulfill my needs.	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
BC3	I feel like a member of this neighborhood.	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
BC4	I belong in this neighborhood.	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
BC5	I have a say about what goes on in my neighborhood.	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
BC6	People in this neighborhood are good at influencing each other.	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
BC7	I feel connected to this neighborhood.	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
BC8	I have a good bond with others in this neighborhood.	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

SD1	What is your total combined family income for the past 12 months <i>(before taxes, from all sources, wages, public assistance/benefits, help from relatives, alimony, and so on? If you don't know your exact income, please estimate)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Less than € 9,999 b. €10,000 - €19,999 c. €20,000 - €49,999 d. €50,000 - €99,999 e. €100,000 - €149,999 f. More than €150,000 g. Choose not to answer
SD2	Occupation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Unemployed b. Employed c. Student d. Retired e. Other.....
SD3	Postal / zip code

HL1	Vision	a. Normal b. Corrected (method of correction.....)
HL2	Hearing	a. Normal b. Corrected (method of correction.....)
HL3	Mental health record	a. No b. Yes, please specify.....
HL4	Neurologic health record	a. No b. Yes, please specify.....
HL5	Consumption of alcohol and/or other psychoactive substances.	a. Often b. Moderated c. Occasional d. No consumption

Please indicate how many hours/minutes per day you have engaged in the below activities in **the last month**.

		On the weekdays (Mon. - Fri.)	On the weekend (Sat. & Sun.)																
ST1	Watching television and/or playing television games (e.g., play station, Wii, Xbox).	<table border="1"> <tr> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Hours</td> <td colspan="3">mins/day</td> </tr> </table>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	Hours	mins/day			<table border="1"> <tr> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Hours</td> <td colspan="3">mins/day</td> </tr> </table>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	Hours	mins/day		
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>																
Hours	mins/day																		
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>																
Hours	mins/day																		
ST2	Using a computer / playing on computers.	<table border="1"> <tr> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Hours</td> <td colspan="3">mins/day</td> </tr> </table>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	Hours	mins/day			<table border="1"> <tr> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Hours</td> <td colspan="3">mins/day</td> </tr> </table>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	Hours	mins/day		
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>																
Hours	mins/day																		
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>																
Hours	mins/day																		
ST3	Playing handheld video games or using handheld devices like handphone to play games/ watch videos (e.g., gameboy, handphone games)	<table border="1"> <tr> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Hours</td> <td colspan="3">mins/day</td> </tr> </table>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	Hours	mins/day			<table border="1"> <tr> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Hours</td> <td colspan="3">mins/day</td> </tr> </table>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	Hours	mins/day		
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>																
Hours	mins/day																		
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>																
Hours	mins/day																		
ST4	Playing/ exercising outdoors (activities that require physical exertion, e.g. in a backyard, walk, bike riding)	<table border="1"> <tr> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Hours</td> <td colspan="3">mins/day</td> </tr> </table>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	Hours	mins/day			<table border="1"> <tr> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Hours</td> <td colspan="3">mins/day</td> </tr> </table>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	Hours	mins/day		
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>																
Hours	mins/day																		
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>																
Hours	mins/day																		
ST5	Family leisure activities (Family BBQ, Park, Picnic, Beach)	<table border="1"> <tr> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Hours</td> <td colspan="3">mins/day</td> </tr> </table>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	Hours	mins/day			<table border="1"> <tr> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> <td><input type="text"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Hours</td> <td colspan="3">mins/day</td> </tr> </table>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	Hours	mins/day		
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>																
Hours	mins/day																		
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>																
Hours	mins/day																		

ABOUT YOU

Before you begin this particular assessment, we would like to ask you to answer a few general questions about yourself: by circling the correct answer or by filling in the space provided.

WH01	What is your gender?	<input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Prefer not to say
WH02	What is your date of birth?	_____ / _____ / _____ Day / Month / Year
WH03	What is the highest education you received?	None at all Primary school Secondary school Tertiary
WH04	What is your marital status?	Single Separated Married Divorced Living as married Widowed
WH05	Are you currently ill?	Yes No
WH06	If something is wrong with your health, what do you think it is?	_____

This assessment asks how you feel about your quality of life, health, or other areas of your life. Please answer all the questions. If you are unsure about which response to give to a question, please choose the one that appears most appropriate. This can often be your first response.

Please keep in mind your standards, hopes, pleasures and concerns. We ask that you think about your life in the last two weeks. For example, thinking about the last two weeks, a question might ask:

	Very poor	Poor	Neither poor nor good	Good	Very good
Do you get the kind of support from others that you need?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

You should tick the number that best fits how much support you got from others over the last two weeks. So, you would tick the number 4 if you got a great deal of support from others as follows.

	Very poor	Poor	Neither poor nor good	Good	Very good
Do you get the kind of support from others that you need?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

You would tick number 1 if you did not get any of the support that you needed from others in the last two weeks. Please read each question, assess your feelings, and circle the number on the scale for each question that gives the best answer for you.

	Very poor	Poor	Neither poor nor good	Good	Very good
WH11	How would you rate your quality of life?				
	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH12	How satisfied are you with your health?				
	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

The following questions ask about **how much** you have experienced certain things in the last four weeks.

	Not at all	A little	A moderate amount	Very much	Extremely
WH13	To what extent do you feel that physical pain prevents you from doing what you need to do?				
	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH14	How much do you need any medical treatment to function in your daily life?				
	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH15	How much do you enjoy life?				
	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH16	To what extent do you feel your life to be meaningful?				
	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH17	How well are you able to concentrate?				
	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH18	How safe do you feel in your daily life?				
	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH19	How healthy is your physical environment?				
	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

The following questions ask about **how completely** you experience or were able to do certain things in the last two weeks.

	Not at all	A little	Moderately	Mostly	Completely
WH10	Do you have enough energy for everyday life?				
	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH11	Are you able to accept your bodily appearance?				
	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH12	Have you enough money to meet your needs?				
	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH13	How available to you is the information that you need in your day-to-day life?				
	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH14	To what extent do you have the opportunity for leisure activities?				
	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

	Very poor	Poor	Neither poor nor good	Good	Very good
WH15	How well are you able to get around?				
	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

The following questions ask you to say **how good or satisfied** you have felt about various aspects of your life over the last two weeks.

		Very dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very satisfied
WH16	How satisfied are you with your sleep?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH17	How satisfied are you with your ability to perform your daily living activities?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH18	How satisfied are you with your capacity for work?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH19	How satisfied are you with yourself?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH20	How satisfied are you with your personal relationships?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH21	How satisfied are you with your sex life?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH22	How satisfied are you with the support you get from your friends?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH23	How satisfied are you with the conditions of your living place?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH24	How satisfied are you with your access to health services?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
WH25	How satisfied are you with your transport?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

The following question refers to **how often** you have felt or experienced certain things in the last two weeks.

		Never	Seldom	Quite often	Very often	Always
WH26	How often do you have negative feelings such as blue mood, despair, anxiety, depression?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

The questions in this scale ask you about your feelings and thoughts during the last month. In each case, please indicate your response by ticking the box representing how often you felt or thought a certain way.

		Never	Almost Never	Sometimes	Fairly often	Very Often
PS1	In the last month, how often have you been upset because of something that happened unexpectedly?	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4
PS2	In the last month, how often have you felt that you were unable to control the important things in your life?	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4
PS3	In the last month, how often have you felt nervous and “stressed”?	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4

PS4	In the last month, how often have you felt confident about your ability to handle your personal problems?	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4
PS5	In the last month, how often have you felt that things were going your way?	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4
PS6	In the last month, how often have you found that you could not cope with all the things that you had to do?	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4
PS7	In the last month, how often have you been able to control irritations in your life?	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4
PS8	In the last month, how often have you felt that you were on top of things?	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4
PS9	In the last month, how often have you been angered because of things that were outside your control?	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4
PS10	In the last month, how often have you felt difficulties were piling up so high that you could not overcome them?	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4

Over the last **two weeks**, how often have you been bothered by any of the following problems?

		Not at all	Several Days	More than half the days	Nearly every day
GA1	Feeling nervous, anxious or on edge	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3
GA2	Not being able to stop or control worrying	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3
GA3	Worrying too much about different things	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3
GA4	Trouble relaxing	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3
GA5	Being so restless that it is hard to sit still	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3
GA6	Becoming easily annoyed or irritable	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3
GA7	Feeling afraid as if something awful might happen	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3

Over the last **two weeks**, how often have you been bothered by any of the following problems?

		Not at all	Several Days	More than half the days	Nearly every day
PH1	Little interest or pleasure in doing things	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3
PH2	Feeling down, depressed, or hopeless	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3
PH3	Trouble falling or staying asleep, or sleeping too much	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3
PH4	Feeling tired or having little energy	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3

PH5	Poor appetite or overeating	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3
PH6	Feeling bad about yourself — or that you are a failure or have let yourself or your family down	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3
PH7	Trouble concentrating on things, such as reading the newspaper or watching television	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3
PH8	Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed? Or the opposite — being so fidgety or restless that you have been moving around a lot more than usual	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3

Annex 2 – NUA digital questionnaires

Day 1 and 5 questionnaire:

How are you feeling at the moment? *

The first picture shows an individual who is very calm, almost sleeping (relaxation, tranquility, idleness, meditation, boredom or laziness). The last picture shows an individual who is bursting with arousal (excitation, euphoria, excitement, rage, agitation, anger).

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

How do you feel at this moment? *

Very Negative

Somewhat Negative

Neutral

Somewhat Positive

 Very Positive

During past 7 days, how would you rate your sleep quality overall? *

0- Terrible 1,2,3 - Poor 4,5,6 - Fair 7,8,9 - Good 10 - Excellent

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Terrible Excellent

Daily Journal *

Is there anything you would like to share about your day?

Enter your answer

Day 2, 3, 4 questionnaire:

How are you feeling at the moment? *

The first picture shows an individual who is very calm, almost sleeping (relaxation, tranquility, idleness, meditation, boredom or laziness). The last picture shows an individual who is bursting with arousal (excitation, euphoria, excitement, rage, agitation, anger).

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

How do you feel at this moment? *

Very Negative

Somewhat Negative

Neutral

Somewhat Positive

Very Positive

Daily Journal *

Is there anything you would like to share about your day?

Enter your answer

Post-recording questionnaire:

How are you feeling at the moment? *

The first picture shows an individual who is very calm, almost sleeping (relaxation, tranquility, idleness, meditation, boredom or laziness). The last picture shows an individual who is bursting with arousal (excitation, euphoria, excitement, rage, agitation, anger).

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

How do you feel at this moment? *

<input type="radio"/> Very Negative	<input type="radio"/> Somewhat Negative
<input type="radio"/> Neutral	<input type="radio"/> Somewhat Positive
<input type="radio"/> Very Positive	

7

Were you alone during the recording? *

- Yes
- No
- Other

8

Where did you perform the recording? *

- At home
- At the site (Outdoors)

9

What activity did you perform during the recording? *

- walking around, looking at spaces around the house
- sitting and relaxing
- cleaning, tidying up
- Other

10

Where did you go in the park? *

Please describe in a couple of sentences where did you spend time in the park during recording.

Enter your answer

11

What did you see during recording? *

Please describe briefly.

Enter your answer

12

If outdoors, what activity did you perform during recording *

- walking around, looking at landscapes
- sitting and relaxing
- Other

13

Did you experience any disturbance during recording? If so, please specify. *

Enter your answer

Submit

Annex 3 – Study instructions manual

EQUIPMENT CARE INSTRUCTIONS

Handle with Care

Adjusting headband: Gently extend the arms — avoid over-extending to prevent damage.

Cleaning: After each use, gently wipe excessive sweat from sensors/skin-contact areas, with alcohol swabs.

Environment protection

Water: Not waterproof — avoid rain, sweat, or liquids

Temperature: Keep away from extreme heat/cold

Bending: Avoid sharp bends near earpieces

Battery & charging

Life: ~5 hours of continuous use
Charge Time: 2.5 hours (charge with provided USB-c cable, preferably in a wall plug).

Troubleshooting

✗ Low signal? Re-adjust headband, clean forehead.

🔄 App crash? Restart the session.

🔋 Low battery? Charge your phone beforehand.

✉ Any other questions or doubts? Check the FAQ sat the QR code below. If you don't find your answer, write us on **WhatsApp (+48) 69777331**

More information

Scan this QR code for more information about the study and the frequently asked questions!

Whatsapp: (+48) 69 777 6331

neuro@neurolandscape.org

www.neurolandscape.org
www.greenincities.eu

NEUROLANDSCAPE

GreenIn
Cities

2025-07

NEUROURBANISM STUDY PARTICIPANT GUIDE

THANK YOU FOR PARTICIPATING!

Follow these steps to ensure smooth data collection.

01 Setting up the EEG headband

Tie back long hair and clean your forehead with the provided alcohol swabs.

Press the button to turn on the device

Adjust the headband to fit snugly behind your ears.

Use your personalized distance mark (from training) to position the device correctly.

02 Using Mind Monitor App

Signal check: Open the app and check the horseshoe symbol

good signal

weak signal readjust

03 Recording

Press the red button to start.

Lock your phone screen; keep it nearby

After 20 minutes, press the white button to stop

Save the file to Dropbox

During **5 days** of duration of the experiment you can choose when you will do the recording, based on your personal schedule and preferences. **Max. 1 recording session per day.** We will need you to record **2 sessions** at home and **1 session** outdoors in the designated green space.

At home recording (2 sessions)

1. Sitting still, record for **1 min** upload file
2. Activities, record for **20 min** upload file.
3. Below are some examples of activities:

DO

- sit
- walk lightly
- tidy up
- other light activities

AVOID

- heat
- water
- screens
- exercise
- sleeping

Outdoors recording (1 session)

1. Start recording only at the park.
2. Sitting/standing still, record for **1 min** upload file
3. Activities, record for **20 min** upload file.
4. Below are some examples of activities:

DO

- slow walk
- sit on a bench
- other non-strenuous outdoor activities

AVOID

- jogging
- picnic
- sports
- other strenuous activities

Daily feedback

Complete short questionnaires on your phone each day. You will receive the questionnaires to whatsapp chat and by e-mail.

Annex 4 – NUA-index- mock-up version

Annex 5 - Step-by-Step Procedure for Data Collection

This procedure presents the steps necessary for the realization of the assessment. These steps occur at the location of the assessment, with the participant present. They take about 1 hour to 1.5 hours for each participant under typical conditions.

Preparation and Pre-Data collection

Key steps in preparation for data collection are activities related to interaction with newly recruited participants. This involves presenting participants with the information sheet that describes the goal of the study, and their rights as participants, notably their right to withdraw participation at any time. This is critical for ethical compliance, and content of the material is dictated by the ethical board who review the assessment procedure. A following step is to record **participant informed consent** (see Figure A2.1) by ensuring that they have understood the information in the information sheet, that any questions they might have been answered. Participants are then invited to sign the consent form, thereby agreeing to participate.

Figure A2.1. NUA participants signing consent forms, during the enrolment meeting, April 2025, Nova Gorica, Slovenia.

After the consent form, key information from the participants is recorded by any technical means, although an online form is most convenient. This information may include their family name, first name, contact number, email, date of enrolment, agreed location and time for return of loaned equipment, and handedness if it is an exclusion criterion. This data is stored in a way that is safe and only accessible to authorized researchers. This information also includes a unique participant code, which allows anonymizing all participant data for the rest of the evaluation.

Study Presentation

Afterwards, participants are then informed about the structure and the steps of the study. The presentation of the study structure to the participants is crucial for

compliance to instructions. It offers a broad overview of what's expected of the participant, how it fits with the research activities, communication with the researcher, as well as overall aspects of the participant's involvement in the study. Broadly, those steps are presented earlier in the content of the present protocol and additionally in the **Annex 3**. The level of details offered to participants should be adequate and just enough for the participants to understand what's expected of them and offer some structure and visibility into the process. It would be important to refrain from sharing with the participant expected outcomes of the studies or hypothesis. If participants have questions around what the expected outcomes for the studies are, they should be told that if they wish further information will be answered at the end of the study.

This presentation can be performed using a narrative form but can be done using audiovisual support, such as a video or recorded presentation, which the participant can be invited to watch alone. Such video was produced for NUA testing and is available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Frnbs-WIR6U&t=1s>.

Technical preparation

This step of the protocol is key in ensuring that the data quality is adequate for further use as well as making sure that participants will show maximal compliance with instructions and procedures.

Setup of applications and participant phone

The first step is to set-up the necessary applications on the participant's phone for objective measures collection. The nature of the technical setup will depend on the way the NUA is implemented. Implementation typically involves the use of at least one application that will be connected through the participant's phone Bluetooth to the recording device. This application additionally records incoming data. The same, or another application is then used to forward the data to a cloud storage for later data analysis. So as not to burden the participants with technical tasks, the researcher performing the assessment will guide the participant closely through the installation or, alternatively with their authorisation, perform on their phone the necessary steps. A key step in this setup is ensuring that the participant code is recorded in the configuration of the recording application. This ensures that the recorded objective measures can be connected through the participant code to corresponding self-report measures. Other steps may include setting recording parameters following device manufacturer recommendation, so that data can be analysed at the best quality.

After the application or applications installation is complete, the participants are presented with the EEG device. The procedure for turning it on is demonstrated to them, and the device is paired to the participant's phone (see example in Figure A2.2). Any challenges in pairing the recording device to the participant's phone are troubleshooted to ensure smooth operations during the follow-up recording as well as when the participants will be performing the recording on their own.

Figure A2.2. NUA Researchers guiding the participants through the necessary app installations. April 2025, Nova Gorica, Slovenia.

Device setup and participant training

Participants are then invited to place the device on the head and forehead, and to adjust it adequately with the help of the researcher.

At this point, researchers may perform measurements on participants' heads to place the device at a standard location on the scalp, if the device has a rigid design. This involves measuring the distance between the inion (the end of skull at the occiput) and the nasion (the bridge of the nose), see Figure A2.3. In recording systems that allow a large coverage of the scalp, head circumference may also be captured. This allows to record the actual location of each sensor on that circumference, for greater accuracy if the goal is to perform precise topographical analysis of the data on the scalp. This is however not required for the full accuracy of the NUA.

Figure A2.3. Establishing a correct placement for mEEG device as an optional step for improving data quality in NUA

Participants are then led through the steps of data recording. These involve:

- Starting the recording application
- Placing the device on the head
- Ensuring using the data from the device is received by the app, which indicates there is Bluetooth connectivity with the phone
- Adjusting device tightness around the head so connectivity is maximized for all electrodes
- Checking the quality of connection for each individual electrodes of the device using dedicated in-app function and following manufacturers indications
- If required, making adjustments to enhance electrode connection, such as device placement, tightness and removal of obstructions to connectivity (e.g. hair...)
- Get ready for recording by ensuring there are no sources of distraction (notably from the phone)
- Pressing the record button on the app to start the recording
- Refraining from excessive head movement during the recording
- Engaging in the activity they must perform during the recording (either the seated rest or activity)
- Stopping the recording in-app, and forwarding the data to the research team through the dedicated cloud connection

After these instructions are offered, participants are also given instructions about how to deal with events such as interruption in the recording, unexpected events occurring that are incompatible with accurate recordings such as an impromptu and unplanned conversation, interruptions, sudden noises, or any kind of emergency that requires them to depart from the prescribed conditions for the recording. In such cases, participants are invited to deal with the interruption and to perform a new recording at the next possible opportunity, or for short term interruption to take note of the event and report it after the recording.

Citizen science and education segment

As part of this first contact with the participants an additional opportunity can be offered to engage participants on the data they are recording.

Participants can be invited to examine the data display in the app that shows real-time recordings of their brain waves activity. They have opportunities to ask questions about what these are, what they mean, and how they can be interpreted. This allows them to be empowered and have a strong enough understanding of what is recorded, what meaning it holds, and how the information will later be used.

Participants can also explore the impact of non-brain activity on the recordings such as eye blinks, and head and body movements. This movement typically results in wide variations that are much larger than those expected coming from brain activity. This is explained to the participant along with the fact that the presence of such movement

renders the data unfortunately unusable for further analysis, which means that their contribution won't have any impact on the results if there are such movements. Participants are then encouraged to refrain from excessive movement during their recording so that the value of their contribution can be preserved and they can fully contribute to the outcome for the assessment.

Objective measures collection

Participants are invited to follow the instructions they received to perform their first recording, the onsite recording at rest.

Rest session

They are then asked to sit at a previously identified place at the site. From that space, they are encouraged to find a restful seated position and to start recording without engaging in any specific task with eyes open for about one minute. At the end of the session, they are encouraged to independently end the recording.

At this juncture, they can ask any questions, and the experimenter monitors their compliance with the instructions and any uncertainty or confusion that may arise. This is important to ensure the quality of their contribution. Furthermore, early issues with connectivity may be solved, as these can be caused by participants' characteristics such as head shape, hair shape and features, or glasses. These can be addressed in the presence of the researcher to ensure participant's continued involvement in troubleshooting and ensuring high data quality.

Walking session

Figure A2.4. Three different NUA participants before and after 20 min walking session.

After the initial issues have been solved, participants are encouraged to carry on with the session autonomously. They are then encouraged to record a second session, the 20-minute session in which they are asked to engage in a leisurely walk across the site (Figure A2.4). After the recording is started and connectivity is assessed, participants are left to explore the space on their own device. At the end of the exploration, in a similar way, they are expected to stop the recording, forward the recording to the researcher through the data sharing service, and to rejoin the researcher.

After on-site data acquisition

Participants are next guided through removing the device from their head and shown maintenance steps. The maintenance steps will vary based on the device manufacturer, but they would typically involve cleaning sensors and ensuring the device battery stays charged and generally taking good care of the device.

Self-report measures collection

Post-Recording Questionnaire

The post-recording questionnaire is an online form sent to the participant automatically after they finish recording, by message or email. That questionnaire contains pre-filled information that include participant code, the day, the time, as well as the site, which allows to track responses. The participants are expected to fill in several questions:

- how they are feeling in the moment capturing their arousal level following a manikin style questionnaire
- how do they feel in the moment capturing their mood from very negative to very positive
- whether they were alone during the recording
- where they performed the recording
- what activity did they perform during the recording (and they have several options: walking around, looking at the space around the house, sitting relaxing, cleaning, tidying up)
- where they went on site if recording was performed outdoor
- what they saw during the recording
- what activity they performed during recording, if outdoors
- whether they experienced any disturbance during recording

The form can be designed conditionally whereby the questions about activity change depending on whether participants declare that the recording was done indoor or outdoor. This avoids confusion and shortens the questionnaire.

Self-Report Measures Collection: long-form questionnaire

Participants are then invited to fill in the self-report measure collection form (full form can be found in **Annex 1**), this is a longer form and may be presented in paper and pencil form, or as an online form (Figure A2.5). They are invited to ask questions if any

of the wording is unclear to them or whether they have confusion about what's expected of them. Participants are invited to fill in the form in a quiet environment which may be indoor or outdoor, near the site of assessment. It is important that privacy is respected during questionnaires completion. The current and suggested list of questionnaires that participants must fill as part of NUA are listed in 3.1.2. Subjective, self-reported measures.

Figure A2.5. NUA participant filling in the questionnaire pack after completing mEEG recording session.

After the participant has finished answering the questionnaire, the experimenter quickly checks that all items of the questionnaires have been properly answered, and no section has been left blank or omitted by mistake by the participant. The participant is then thanked for providing their answers and told that they will now receive further information about what will be expected of them for the rest of the study on that day as well as in the following week.

Closing steps

The closing part of the assessment involves some administrative tasks. Participants are reminded of their tasks during the duration of the recording period at home. They are given the device in a bag with a pamphlet. The pamphlet records the key steps they're going to have to go through during the recording, as well as frequently asked questions that will help them navigate any issues, and a reminder to contact the research team if there are any difficulties they encounter.

Participants are asked whether they have any further questions and are left to go home with the device and the instructions.

At-home recording procedures

The data acquisition period during the home segments involves objective measures collection, and the follow-up post-recording questionnaires. The protocol is identical to the one conducted on site and is as taught to the participant during the first assessment. Recordings are thereby performed by the participants alone according to the prescribed schedule.

Figure A2.6. NUA participant recording her EEG signal at home.

It may also include an additional daily online self-report questionnaire that captures participants' day-to-day mood and experiences. This is kept short and is sent automatically through instant messages or email at the same time every day for the duration of the home segment.

If there are any challenges encountered by the participants during this stage, support should be in place to ensure the recording is continuing. This also entails monitoring data quality, and participant compliance with the protocol.

At the end of the assessment period, an appointment for the final meeting with the participants is scheduled. This allows participants to return the device and receive the first part of their compensation for the study, if any. This ends their participation in the campaign of data collection.

Follow-up assessment and follow-up timepoints

For follow-up assessment, the procedures are identical. Because participants have already filled in a consent form, they do not need to go through that procedure again. The other procedures should, however, stay the same. Because of the potentially long-term interval between assessments, it's important that participants are reminded of

the protocol, what's expected of them, the required steps, as well as the instructions they will be asked to follow. This should be done in person in a narrative form as well as with the support of the pamphlet or audiovisual materials, as during the first assessment.

If the assessment is the final assessment in a series, for instance in the case of a second assessment or at the end of a campaign of continuous assessment, participants can be thanked again for their participation and offered to receive an update on the outcome of the assessment and its impact. This would be the final contact with the participants and the last step of the protocol.

Automated processes for data acquisition procedure

To facilitate assessment implementation and reduce impact on resources, segments of the task involved can be automated. These tasks include managing the recording after participants have saved them, sending participants surveys and questionnaires they must fill-in during the assessment in their preferred language, or sending automated communication such as appointment reminders.

This automation can be broken down in two independent components. The first involves sending to the participant a general questionnaire and communication at set times. The questionnaires that are sent may vary for opening and closing days, or assessment days and be made available in the participant preferred communication language. The automation structure for this daily questionnaire is presented in Figure A2.7-A. Another component of the automation includes tasks that must be performed right after the participant has recorded neurophysiological data. These tasks are triggered after a recording is received by the participant. This involves uploading the data to cloud storage for safe backup and later data analysis, keeping track of the number of recordings and their timing, and sending participants a post-recording questionnaire that captures crucial information about where the recording was performed. The specific automation structure for this aspect of the data is presented in Figure A2.7-B.

These automations can be implemented as part of an in-house data acquisition application or on a third-party automation platform. Suitable platforms include business automation platforms that offer EU-based servers and allow connecting various cloud services such as data storage, emailing, calendars, messaging and translation, with spreadsheets or databases where limited participant information is securely stored.

Figure A2.7. Automation steps for NUA data acquisition protocol. A. Automation delivering daily questionnaires and key communication. B. Automation implementing data processing and acquisition steps after resident-led data acquisition.

Annex 6 – Data Analysis Pipeline and Preprocessing Steps

A6.1 Preparing physiological data for use

EEG Data Preprocessing

The first step in data preprocessing is the export of the data from the device onto the data analysis computer or server. This is not an especially complicated or challenging task; therefore, we should not go into details on its steps. The only point of concern is making sure that as the data is transferred, important information such as the participant code to which the data is attached is preserved in the file name. As part of the data management procedure, a specific protocol can be set up to ensure that, as the data is exported from the device, it is named with a participant code, recording time, and a reference number for the device the data was recorded on.

The next step in data preprocessing typically involves converting the data from the proprietary format of the device manufacturer into a portable standard file format. There are many options for such file formats, but a file format that is often used by neuroscientists is the EDF file format. It allows and facilitates data exchange across platforms and typically can be produced from EEG data output from any manufacturer. Many manufacturers often offer tools for data export towards EDF format or offer to save data exported in that EDF format directly.

Data Integrity Check

The next step after data export is the data integrity check. This can be done by opening the EDF file within the data analysis and visualization package (e.g. in EEGLAB). Upon opening the data, the information contained in the header is accessible and should be examined. This information includes the number of EEG channels, sampling rate, duration, and length of the recording. It is important to check that both these values and the data that is being displayed in the analysis package matches expected values. That check from the header data using inspection, or as part of an automated preprocessing pipeline. Visual check of the recorded data can be done using the data display function of the analysis package and involves verifying that the number of recorded channels and recording durations are as expected. Any discrepancy should be flagged. Another important step in checking data integrity is visually monitoring the traces of the data for odd artifacts such as abrupt shifts in recorded values, pronounced drifts in data traces, random values, lack of continuity in values, and any generally striking or unusual patterns in the data. Examples of typical artifacts can be found in Cohen, 2014.

The next step in checking data integrity is to ensure that any **event markers** that were recorded along with the data are present in the file that has been imported. Not all recordings will include those markers, but in some devices, they can be present, notably indicating the effective start of the recording, the end of the recording, or moments in which the recording was paused.

Filtering

The following step in data analysis is filtering. The goal of filtering is to remove any unwanted fluctuations due to noisy sources from the EEG data. These may be slow drifts that are reflected in low frequencies variations in the data, faster sudden changes in the data, or continuous noise that are reflected by high frequencies variations. These may also include specific artefactual frequencies such as oscillations due to environmental noise produced by an electrical outlet or an electrical appliance that emit electromagnetic waves. Based on the country in which the data is recorded, those single frequency artifacts will be typically at 50 Hertz in the EU and the harmonics of those frequencies, for instance at 100 Hertz or 120 Hertz respectively, although these higher harmonics are rarely captured by typical commercial devices used in mobile EEG.

To remove these unwanted frequencies, filtering is used. Typically, single frequency artifacts at 50 Hertz or 60 Hertz are removed using a notch filter that targets these frequencies. Low frequencies that appear in the data as slow drift are removed using a high-pass filter. A suitable setting for the high-pass filter is typically 0.5 Hertz. The high frequencies are removed using a low-pass filter. The recommended setting for the low-pass filter may vary widely, a recommended setting for the NUA methodology is 40 Hertz. The design and nature of the filter will typically vary with software packages, but a good choice of filter type typically available in most data analysis packages is the Butterworth filter, of which a second-order Butterworth filter is typically preferred for this methodology (Cohen, 2014; Luck, 2014).

Artifact removal

The next step in data analysis is artifact removal. For this task, we favour the use of an **Independent Component Analysis** approach. It is a data processing tool that is used when there is a need to separate mixed signals into their independent underlying sources. In EEG data artifact removal, sources that are especially of interest are eyeblinks, heart rate, muscle movements, eye movement, as well as other movement-related artifacts that show consistent patterns over time. ICA can be applied and used to first identify the components that represent these various artifacts, to remove those sources from the decomposed data, and to back-project the data from the component space into the original channel data structure without the presence of the artefactual component. This effectively removes any variation from the data that have their source in artefactual. This yields cleaner EEG data that is more likely to only contain variations and fluctuations directly related to brain activity as opposed to non-brain related signals. This renders working with the data more efficient, because it is less prone to noise and to random variations that may mask or hide underlying patterns of interest in the brain data.

A further step in artifact removal involves inspecting the data visually for the presence of remaining noise, missing channels, or noisy channels. Any noisy channels or missing channels can be either removed or, if the data integrity must be maintained in terms of

number of channels to facilitate further processing, they can be **interpolated** using data from neighbouring channels. It is important to note that when a channel is noisy or missing and is interpolated that way, the data for that channel is lost, and the data that is contained in a new interpolated channel is merely a weighted average of the neighbouring channels. Therefore, while the channel obtains new data based on neighbouring recordings, the original information at this location cannot be retrieved and is lost. It is merely a means to maintain the data integrity and number of channels across participants, which facilitates further analysis. Indeed, if several participants were to have different numbers of channels, and those channels missing at random, this would complicate handling of the data, checking of the data, averaging, and integration of the data across participants.

Data segmentation

A further, optional, step in data preprocessing is segmenting the data into sections of segments or **epochs**. This epoch duration may be variable but duration of over 8 seconds offers enough data for further processing, notably by allowing time-frequency transformation to operate in the best conditions (Cohen, 2014). This duration also facilitates further screening of the data for artifacts as enough length is available if artefacts are identified visually.

This leads us to the next data preprocessing stage, which involves screening those epochs for unusual, excessively large changes in voltage. These artifacts can remain due to electrode displacement, shifts in recorded voltage or sweat at the scalp, which would appear as large drift in the data that cannot be removed by filtering. This process would typically be done automatically.

Spectral power analysis

After data preprocessing has concluded, the data can enter spectral power analysis. Spectral power analysis involves transforming the data from the time domain into the frequency domain by using a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). This transformation yields power density values ($\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$) for each of the eight-second epochs. The values represent how much various frequencies are present in the signal. For the NUA methodology, two frequency bands are of interest: the Alpha Band between 8 and 13 Hertz and the Beta band between 14 and 30 Hertz (A. Olszewska-Guizzo et al., 2018; Olszewska-Guizzo, Fogel, Escoffier, et al., 2022). These have been further covered in an earlier section. As part of the data analysis, the values corresponding to these frequency bands are extracted from the Fast Fourier Transform and averaged across each of those bands. This yields one value for the Alpha band and one value for the Beta band for each of the data segments.

If the methodology setup allows collecting a baseline data for each participant first, Fourier transform can be performed also for that baseline data. The baseline values can then be subtracted from each epoch computed at the earlier stage. This is helpful because it allows accounting for individual differences in baseline EEG activity, therefore

contributing to reducing the variability in the data that is not linked to the brain response of interest.

This last step closes the EEG data preprocessing stage, and the data is ready for statistical analysis.

A6.2 Preparing self-report data for use

The preparation of self-report data for statistical analysis is much less involved than the preparation of brain data. There are, however, several steps to approaching this data that are crucial in ensuring reliable outcomes from the assessment.

The first step is ensuring the data is recorded so it can be further exploited for data analysis under electronic format. If the data was collected using a pen and paper methodology, this will involve copying participants' answers to surveys and questionnaires to an electronic database format, either directly, or through a custom-designed form, tools such as Excel or Google Sheets.

Once the data is stored in electronic form, several verifications must be performed. The first is to scan for possible personal identifiers in the data. This is unlikely to occur for structured surveys, but it is possible that it may occur in a free-form input field such as the kind of journaling data that are recorded as part of the assessment. Any kind of potentially identifying data can be suppressed or deleted at the time of data input in an electronic format. Furthermore, the corresponding data on the original storage, be it paper or electronic, must be redacted accordingly to protect participant privacy.

The following step in ensuring that data is ready for use is to check for potential missing data. This is ideally done immediately after the participant has finished filling the data so that the participant can be asked to complete the required information right away. However, it's possible that some missing answers have escaped this initial first screening, and if that's the case, a record must be kept of potential missing data for a given participant. Participants can then complete the missing data, if they wish, at a later time.

An important verification that must be performed on self-report data is to check for random or extreme entries in the participants inputs. Extreme responses will constitute outliers and may skew data analysis and therefore compromise the accuracy of the assessment. Random, rather than meaningful and consistent responses, would reflect a careless response profile potentially indicating that the participants may have provided fill in the survey without proper attention. If such a pattern is found in the data, the data should be flagged accordingly for that participant and evaluated further downstream for exclusion to protect the integrity of the assessment output.

The last step in the preparation for the use of self-report data for analysis is the scoring of the standardized instruments. Each series of answers provided by the participants for the instrument must be summed following the instructions from the original creators of the instrument. One must be careful of checking whether some items are reverse-coded. This means that the answers for these items should be subtracted

instead of added to the overall score from the instrument. Following these steps, the final score will then be stored in a database that will hold the results for the measure.

A6.3 Statistical analysis strategies for EEG and Self-report data

This section presents the strategies for data analysis for both the EEG data and the self-report data. This analysis is performed with statistical modelling with the goal of providing human-readable results for this assessment. Self-report data and physiological data are processed in a similar way.

The goal of the statistical processing of the data is to derive two crucial pieces of information about the outcome of the analysis: the estimate for the value of a measure and an estimate of its variability.

Deriving a robust estimate of measurements

The first step involves computing an estimate of the value that is measured. This is done by typically computing the average of the measured values. For instance, the average will be computed over all the participants in the assessments for power measures in Alpha Band, or for scores of a given set of self-report questionnaires.

Additional steps may be taken to develop a more robust estimate. The use of the average presents some challenges, because it is very sensitive to potential outlier measures in the record (Osborne & Overbay, 2004). In the cases where, because of issues with the assessment or inter-individual differences, a participant shows a value that is out of range with the other participants, there can be a bias of the average towards that participant's value, therefore obscuring the overall pattern in the population. To protect against this possibility, outliers may be removed from the data. A strategy that is often used is to compute the standard deviation of the measurement (that is, how spread out the measurement is) and cut off values that are too extreme and fall farther from the average than 3 or 4 times the standard deviation (Bakker & Wicherts, 2014).

Estimating the variability of measurements

However, in the context of the NUA, deriving an estimate is not sufficient to provide all the information that is captured by the assessment. A crucial step for the interpretation of the measurements is estimating their variability. The variability indicates how consistent the measurement is across the sample and the neighbourhood population. For instance, one may consider an alpha brain response that is very consistent across all participants in the assessment, varying little and showing a pattern that is widely shared among participants. Conversely, another sample may show wide variation in the alpha response across participants in each neighbourhood sample, which would indicate large variability within a population, likely linked to diversity in the population connected to socio-economic factors or other sources that would be important to integrate in the interpretation of the assessment.

To estimate a measure of the variability, the sample is processed, and a confidence interval is computed based on the series of values for each measurement (Cumming et al., 2012). The confidence intervals provide an estimate of where the true measurement for the overall population is likely to fall. It has two key components. The first is an actual interval that indicates the bounds of the most likely higher and lower values for the measurement. For instance, if the average estimate for a questionnaire is 6 points on the scale, the confidence interval will provide a range that could be, for instance, 5.5 and 6.5, thereby indicating a range in which the true mean value of the measurement most likely lies. This provides information about the reliability and variability in measurements because the wider the interval, the more variable the sample is, and the narrower the interval, the more consistent the measure is across participants in the sample.

The second key piece of information that defines a confidence interval is a confidence level. This captures the degree of confidence for the interval, and it is decided before data analysis starts. While the theoretical underpinnings of this percentage are complex, it nonetheless gives information about how likely the true mean value is to fall within the interval. For instance, one could consider the interval that was taken as an example earlier. If the confidence level is computed at a 95% confidence level, which is a widely used value, it would indicate a high likelihood that this specific confidence interval will contain the true mean for the measurement across repeated assessments.

A key advantage of confidence intervals is that they allow inferences to be made about differences between time points of the measurement. This is helpful in determining whether the outcome of the assessment differs significantly between a first time point and a second time point, or between sites. This provides information on whether a specific change in the urban environment has made an impact on population wellbeing as measured by the NUA. Notably, if the confidence intervals between two sets of measurements do not overlap, then it can be concluded that the differences in estimates between the two measurements are significant, and therefore the intervention likely made a difference (Smithson, 2003). An example of non-overlapping intervals would be between 4.5 and 5.5 for one measurement and between 2 and 3.5 for another, reflecting a likely effect of the intervention. On the other hand, if the intervals overlap, this suggests that differences in measurement are due random variations and do not reflect real change, or that these changes are too subtle to be reflected in the resident sample involved in the assessment.

Refining estimates of measurements and variability: accounting for individual differences

To further increase the reliability of both the estimate as well as the variability, more advanced statistical analysis techniques can be deployed. This involves using statistical models that allow the integration of both the measurement of interest (for instance, Alpha Power or a self-report measure) and measures of individual differences (Stroup et al., 2024). These measures would typically be socio-economic variables such as gender, income, and other assessments of background that are captured as part of a

demographic section in the NUA assessment. Explicitly integrating the influence of those individual characteristics on the changes in measurement outcomes allows their effect to be controlled. This reduces their influence on the measurement, which makes the assessment closer to its likely real value and makes it easier to detect changes. This also has a positive impact on the measure of variability and therefore on the computation of confidence intervals (Wang et al., 2019). These can then be more precise, which allows more subtle changes in neighbourhood participant responses before and after assessment to be detected. Furthermore, because inter-individual differences are considered, there is enhanced comparability between neighbourhoods with different socio-economic characteristics. It is important to note that this may not always be desirable, because these differences may be meaningful, and in some situations, it may be important to preserve their impact on the measurement and its variability. In these situations, using this statistical strategy should be avoided.

Annex 7 - Relevant initiatives and potential for NUA integration

Project name	Funding scheme/ year(s)	Brief description	reference
environMENTAL	Horizon Europe, 2021 - 2025	is examining how climate change, pollution, and urban environment affect brain health across 1+ million Europeans, using MRI scans and environmental data to link exposure to mental health outcomes	www.environmental-project.org/
New European Bauhaus	EC Initiative (2021)	Three pillars of NEB initiatives include sustainability, aesthetic and inclusive built environment and urban renovation. NUA corresponds to all three pillars, especially emphasizing the quality of human experience through the lens of wellbeing and quality of life.	https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/index_en
eMOTIONAL Cities	H2020, 2021-2025	joins urban planning, neuroscience and ICT. It uses natural experiments in multiple cities (e.g. Copenhagen, Lisbon, London, and Detroit) to measure neural and physiological responses to urban conditions . The project produces "eMOTIONAL city mapping" by overlaying spatial social/health metrics with neuroscience experiment results . Its objective is to fully characterize urban health inequalities by understanding the brain processes underlying citizens' reactions to city stimuli .	https://emotionalcities-h2020.eu/
Clever Cities Project	Horizon 2020 (2018 – 2023)	Co-designing Locally tailored Ecological solutions for Value added, socially inclusive Regeneration in Cities. An EU-funded initiative demonstrating the role of urban greenery in improving mental health.	https://clevercities.eu/
Urbinat Project	Horizon 2020 (2018 - 2024)	Healthy corridors as drivers of social housing neighbourhoods for the co-creation of social, environmental and marketable NBS. The project supports participatory co-creation methodologies in urban design	https://urbinate.eu/
Council of Europe Landscape Convention	CM/Rec(2025)1 by Council of Europe	CM/Rec(2025)1 on Landscape and Health, which underscores the critical role of landscape quality in public health; approved the proposals of the International Jury and CDCPP on the 8 th Session of the Council of Europe Landscape Award (Strasbourg, 14-15 May 2024)	https://www.coe.int/en/web/landscape/home

Annex 8 – Software and Hardware Selection Criteria for NUA

A8.1 Software

Each of the steps for treating the NUA- acquired data (data analysis (pre-processing) and statistical analysis, involves a specialized software. The best strategy to pick a software package is first to inquire whether the experts have any preference or tool they already have familiarity with. Another criterion of selection is cost of the license, for example some pre-processing software are standalone, and free, and some full under the MATLAB license, which is costly. In this case, if cost is a concern, other options include Brainstorm and any packages running on Python, notably MNE Python.

Data analysis tools

A complete coverage of all the data analysis tools used for EEG is beyond the scope of this methodology, as these are constantly evolving. However, we wish to list a few options to facilitate the implementation of NUA in a variety of settings.

Some of the most readily available packages and analysis software are used within signal processing frameworks such as **MATLAB** by MathWorks or **Python**. A Python tool is MNE Python, which is an open-source software used for EEG data analysis, that includes functionalities such as preprocessing and time-frequency analysis. Another option is the MATLAB-based EEGLAB, which also includes several standard preprocessing stages such as filtering as well as more advanced analysis and preprocessing such as Independent Component Analysis (ICA). It also offers visualization tools and data export tools. An alternative to EEGLAB in MATLAB is the FieldTrip Toolbox, which is designed for EEG analysis but also offers the option to analyse electrode and physiological data of all types as well. It has preprocessing tools, visualization, statistical analysis, as well as source localization. The last option running in a MATLAB environment is Brainstorm. This is a free, open-source software used for EEG analysis, as well as other modalities such as MEG and fMRI. It has a powerful visualization tool that allows displaying results on 2D and 3D rendering of the scalp and the brain, as well as a source modelling tool. It also includes all the important steps for data analysis. Regarding Brainstorm, it is important and helpful to note that while it is developed using MATLAB and is based on that framework, it does not require owning a MATLAB license to run as it can run standalone. This can save costs.

Tools for Statistical Analysis

This section will briefly describe the tools that may be suitable for the statistical analysis step of the NUA assessment. Several tools can be used for the statistical modelling of the measurements. Listing those tools and the pros and cons of those tools is beyond the scope of this document. We are succinctly listing a few of the alternative software packages that can be suitable to different contexts. These tools fall into two broad categories.

The first category includes programming-based tools that require an ability to and ease with coding and script writing. These tools include free and/or open-source software such as R, which is one of the most comprehensive and most popular tools for these types of data analysis. An alternative is Python, which is a general-purpose scripting and development language that has packages that can be used for statistical modelling. The last commercial alternative is MATLAB, which also has functions that allow statistical modelling of the kind of data that are exploited by NUA. Some of these tools have the advantage of being free and readily available, such as R or Python, which makes them good choices to lift financial barriers for the implementation of the methodology. However, because they require the use of programming skills, they may not be suitable to all experts, and alternatives in the following second category may be better suited in that case.

The second set of tools are tools that do not require any programming skills and allow analysis to be performed fully through a graphical interface. These include established commercial statistical packages such as **SPSS, Stata, or SAS**. These tools present the advantage of their accessibility to users who do not know coding; they are, however, more expensive alternatives which may limit availability in some contexts.

A8.2 Hardware

EEG device selection

A crucial step in implementing the present methodology is the selection of the proper EEG recording device. This is important because the novelty in this methodology rests on the way it integrates recent and ongoing advancements in EEG devices as was discussed in earlier sections.

In the following section we will present the criteria that are crucial in identifying an adequate EEG device for use with the NUA methodology. Because the goal of this methodology presentation is not to provide detailed guidance on the complexities of selecting such a device, we will only present **key considerations** to keep in mind for decision making.

Devices should be **wireless**, offer **storage capacity** as well as **battery capacity for up to 8 hours** ideally. They should also offer a sampling rate that is sufficient to capture the frequencies of interest for the present methodology, namely Alpha and Beta waves. As these frequencies go up to 40 Hertz per second, signal processing theory indicates that the sampling rate should be at the bare minimum twice that last frequency, 80 Hertz at the minimum (Nyquist, 2009). In practice and to obtain a better-quality signal, it should be **higher than 100 Hz**. Most mobile EEG devices available on the market (see Table 7) would fit that criterion however because they offer data recording at a typical minimal sampling frequency of 128 Hertz. When possible, it would be better for further data analysis and processing if the sampling rate of the device is close to 256 Hertz, as this results in a higher quality recording, assuming the device is not significantly heavier or bulkier.

Figure A8.1. Muse 2 mEEG headband. It is lightweight, wireless and allows freedom of movement. It connects to the smartphone via Bluetooth and allows viewing the signal quality and recording progress by the participant.

This leads us to the concern of size and weight, as the present methodology is for mobile applications. Devices should be **small, light, allow freedom of movement**, to allow participants to wear them as they go about their daily tasks unbothered, without compromising usability for the participant or robustness of the device and difficulties in maintenance. The device should also be able to output the recording in a standard file format that can be easily transmitted to a computer and open for further analysis.

A search for a suitable device can be performed using relevant sources of information including manufacturer websites, research forums, as well as review publications that have focused on mEEG research. Relevant data can be gathered from those sources and sorted in a table based on the priorities as suggested in this section. As an illustration of the outcome of such a process we are sharing in Table A8.1 the results from a survey performed as part of the data acquisition exercise within GreenInCities.

Type of electrodes

In line with the technological advancement presented in an earlier section, device characteristics that are crucial for the present methodology. The first is the use of dry electrodes, as Ts are faster and easier to set up, which makes them suitable for use by research participants in a citizen science context. Another important characteristic of the devices used for the NUA methodology is that it would when possible use active electrodes, as they allow to offset the impact of noise and movement, when people are freely moving in their everyday environment.

Electrode placement selection

Further criteria for EEG device selection are the **number and placement of recording electrodes, reference electrodes**, as well as additional **recording sensors**. In what follows, we will present why those criteria are important for EEG recording in the context of the NUA methodology. We will also address the related trade-offs when deciding on those criteria. This is an important point to address because electrode location, as well as number of electrodes used for EEG recording, has been a recent topic of conversation in Neurourbanism research (Gramann, 2024). We will therefore present recommendations for electrode location for the present methodology as well as the rationale for these choices in the context of current research.

Why does electrode placement matter?

The origin of the electric signals produced by the brain has an impact on where on the scalp the signal will be recorded. It is therefore crucial that the location of the electrodes that will pick up this signal match with where the underlying sources of electrical activity are expected to appear at the scalp. If these electrode locations do not match expected locations, they run the risk of failing to record the right signals, missing relevant, or recording irrelevant, brain activity.

The correct location for electrode placement for a particular purpose is typically determined by looking at prior studies that investigated the processes and brain responses that are of interest. For the NUA methodology, the relevant literature is the Neurourbanism literature reviewed earlier which primarily involve the front of the scalp (over the frontal and pre-frontal lobes of the brain), and the back of the scalp and exclude the less relevant central locations at the top of the scalp. The electrodes placement selected for NUA does not however exclude the potential discovery of new signals that can constitute helpful pointers for future research.

Why does the number of electrodes matter?

There has been an increasingly present debate in the Neurourbanism literature on what is the appropriate number of electrodes to use for EEG recording in the field. Some authors have advocated for the largest possible number of electrodes, typically 24 or more electrodes placed evenly to cover most upper and lateral of the scalp excluding the face (Gramann, 2024). The argument is that these electrodes numbers offer an almost complete coverage of the scalp and allow capturing with greater precision signals from underlying neural sources irrespective of where they might fall on the scalp. This is presented as having the advantage of not missing any potential novel signals, of having enough redundancy in data recording to prevent signal loss by facilitating channel interpolation. It also renders artifact rejection techniques such as ICA more effective (Delorme & Martin, 2021). Potentially it would also offer sufficient spatial coverage to allow the use of algorithms to back-compute the location of the underlying neural source within the brain. This can be helpful in a research perspective to compare

findings with neural imaging techniques such as functional magnetic resonance imaging.

While advantages of having a greater number of electrodes are valid in the research laboratory as well as in some field experiments, using a greater number of electrodes becomes a disadvantage for data recording performed in the field with residents' involvement. For the goals of NUA the main disadvantage is that a greater number of electrodes will need a larger and heavier amplifier for the data to be processed and recorded. It will also lead to using a larger storage size, which will make for a bulkier device. This would make the recording hardware inconvenient for use by the participants without the assistance of the research team. In addition, these devices would also be much more expensive, making them impractical for loan to participants, because of potential financial liability. Furthermore, a greater number of electrodes translates to a more time-consuming and more complicated recording setup. Setting up too many electrodes would need training, and would be too challenging and too time consuming, leading to poor compliance, poor electrode setup, thereby resulting in noisy, unreliable, and improperly recorded data, potentially increased drop-out rates. Together this would compromise the reliability of the assessment, while leading to pressure and frustration from participation for the residents.

While the advantages of having a higher number of electrodes are real, they are only marginal and present diminishing returns in the context of NUA methodology. For the first implementation of the NUA methodology as part of the GreenInCities project, we opted for using a device with as many electrodes as possible given all the previous items (location, lightweight, mobile, user-friendly) are ticked, and that device has 4 EEG channels. Considering all these parameters, the choice was made to use the mEEG equipment in the Muse2 headband by Interaxon as it best serves the purposes of this first iteration of NUA (see Figure A8.)

Table A8.1. mEEG devices considered for NUA with comparison to the final selection- Muse2 Headband.

Company	Model	Cost	Design	Sampling Rate (Hz)	Type of electrode	EKG	Channels (Refs + Aux)	Montage	Gyro / Acc	Ease of Setup	Setup Time (Min)	Self-applied Data Quality	Experimental-applied Data Quality	Maintenance Resilience	Onboard Recording?	Battery Life	Data Export Cost
Emotiv	Epoch X	***	Helmet	128/256	Semi-dry saline	No	14+2	10-20 (AF3, F7, F3, etc.)	Yes	4	15 (5-10)	Average	Fair to good	5	No, requires laptop/tablet	6hr	Requires raw data access license
Emotiv	MN8	**	Headset	~64	Dry	No	2+4	Non-standard, ear canal	Yes	8	Few minutes	Poor	Fair	8	No, requires laptop/tablet	6hr	No raw data access
Emotiv	Insight	**	Headset	128	Semi-dry	No	5+	10-20 (AF3, AF4, etc.)	Yes	5	15 (5)	Average	Fair	7	No, requires laptop/tablet	20hr	Needs raw data access license
NeuroSky	MinWave Mobile 2	*	Headset	512	Dry	No	1+2	10-20 (FP1)	?	8	5	Average	Fair	9	No, requires laptop/tablet	6hr	Paid software
Brain Products	LiveAmpl	***	Fabric cap	1000	Any type (A)	Yes	8 or 16 + bipolar options	10-20 flexible	Yes	N/A	20	Very good	Very good	2	No	4hr	Paid recording software
Interaxon	Muse 2 Headband	**	Headset	256	Dry	Yes	4+3	10-20 (TP9/10, AF9/8)	Yes	8	5	Poor to average	Fair	9	No, app-based	5hr	Low-cost software
Advanced Brain Monitoring	Be-Alert X10	***	Helmet	256	Saline	Yes	9+1	Oct-20	Yes	N/A	15	Fair to good	Fair to good	4	No, requires laptop/tablet	8hr	None
Bittium	BrainStatus	***	Headset	256	Saline	No	10+4+EOG	10-20 (FP2, AF8, etc.)	No	5	5	Good	Good	8	Yes, requires tablet	na	NA

Typical cost: * < 300 EUR; ** 300-1000 EUR; *** >1000 EUR. Cost euro estimate May 2024 does not consider possible discounts. Active electrodes systems are marked as (A) in Type of electrode column

Annex 9 – Standards and Norms Underpinning the NUA Methodology

The Neurourbanism Assessment (NUA) is conducted in accordance with the following internationally recognised ethical, scientific, and technical standards and norms:

A9.1. Ethical Standards

1.1. General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, EU 2016/679)

Regulation governing the processing of personal data within the EU. NUA adheres to GDPR for the collection, storage, transfer, and use of participants' sensitive data.

1.2. Minimal Risk Classification

NUA classifies its procedures as “minimal risk,” i.e., no greater than those encountered in daily life or routine psychological assessments, as per ethical guidelines in biomedical and behavioural research.

1.4. Informed Consent Protocol

All participants are fully informed of the study's purpose, procedures, risks, and data management practices, and must voluntarily consent in writing. Withdrawal is allowed at any point without penalty.

1.5. Right to Privacy and Withdrawal

Participants are assured their data will remain confidential and that any data collected prior to withdrawal will not be used, consistent with best practices in psychological research ethics.

A9.2. Scientific and Research Integrity Standards

2.1. ALLEA European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity

Provides principles for good scientific practice including reliability, honesty, respect, and accountability in research design, methods, and reporting.

2.3. Ecological Validity Principle

All physiological data in NUA is collected in real-world environments rather than laboratory simulations to ensure findings are generalizable to daily urban life.

2.4. Validated Preprocessing Pipelines for EEG and HRV

NUA employs industry-standard preprocessing techniques for artifact detection, noise filtering, and signal correction (e.g., ICA, ASR), consistent with best practices in electrophysiological research.

A9.3. Technical and Safety Standards

3.1. CE Marking (Conformité Européenne)

All mobile EEG devices used in NUA are consumer-grade, non-invasive, and CE-certified for use within the European Economic Area, guaranteeing compliance with safety, health, and environmental protection standards.

3.2. Electrical Safety Standards for Portable EEG Devices

Devices used (e.g., Muse 2) comply with IEC 60601-1 for electrical safety in medical devices and related standards required for CE certification.

A9.4. Project-Specific Norms and Policies

4.1. GreenInCities Deliverable D1.8 – Data Management Plan

Outlines specific procedures for secure data collection, processing, anonymisation, sharing, and long-term storage in the context of the GreenInCities project.

4.2. GreenInCities Deliverable D4.1 – Ethics and Data Requirements

Details ethical compliance expectations for the use of neurophysiological data and participant engagement practices across the project.